

Deliverable 2.4 Synthesis of the final Regional Scalability Plans

Imprint

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MERLIN Key messages

1. The 17 MERLIN Regional Scalability Plans (RSPs) offer visions for upscaling restoration at wider landscape levels with a time horizon up to 2050 created through collaborative efforts to upscale freshwater restoration initiatives. The RSPs address 'why', 'where', 'what', 'how', and 'who' questions to upscale freshwater restoration.
2. The RSPs mainstream Nature-based Solutions (NbS) thinking and interaction with stakeholders towards common goals.
3. The starting point for developing an ambitious and feasible regional scale-up plan requires insight into current approaches to restoring freshwater ecosystems. The MERLIN case studies differed greatly in this regard which determined the scope and content of their RSPs.
4. Upscaling freshwater ecosystem restoration entails mainstreaming Nature-based Solutions (NbS) into policies and practices and interaction with stakeholders towards common goals. In MERLIN, this has been done through the EU Green Deal ambitions.
5. Biodiversity net gain, climate change mitigation and inclusivity are the main EU Green Deal goals of the RSPs.
6. The RSPs highlight that transformative change requires actions in three areas: practical work in the field, changes in policies, and efforts to involve the public. To successfully restore freshwater on a large scale, all these actions need to work together.
7. It is essential that upscaling entails replication and expansion of current good practices as well as the development of inclusive multiple benefit projects for nature, climate, water as well as society and economy.
8. Mainstreaming restoration requires collaboration and collective action with diverse set of actors. The RSPs highlight the need to build new coalitions and cross-sectoral collaboration as well as strengthen existing networks.
9. Forming multidisciplinary teams that address the biophysical, socioeconomic, legal and financial aspects is critical to the overarching success of RSPs.
10. Adapting plans and measures due to changing conditions (e.g. climate change, land use) is key to ensuring long-term success.
11. A well embedded monitoring strategy and monitoring systemic impacts of freshwater restoration is needed to better understand the impact of restoration on nature, society and the economy. This in turn can lead to better appreciation and support.

MERLIN Executive Summary

Upscaling restoration entails restoring degraded ecosystems at a large scale and is urgently needed to respond to the biodiversity and climate crises. In the MERLIN project, upscaling of freshwater ecosystem restoration is taken forward through **Regional Scalability Plans (RSPs) that extend restoration activities to a wider landscape and entail long-term planning (2025-2050)**. During 2021-2024, each of the 17 MERLIN case studies has co-designed a Regional Scalability Plan (RSP) with their key stakeholders. The basis for these plans was formed by case study optimization strategies (Buijse et al. 2022) and stakeholder collaboration through case study advisory boards. The early draft plans, summarized in interim RSPs (Pietilä et al, 2023) have matured into final plans. As the MERLIN case studies had very diverse starting points, also the RSPs are very diverse in terms of concreteness and the level of current implementation of the plans.

The RSPs go beyond single measures and aim at wider landscapes, often at larger watershed scale, or national scale. The RSP design incorporates Nature-based Solutions thinking to ensure multiple benefits to the environment and society. The individual RSPs as well as this synthesis provide frameworks and measures for upscaling freshwater restoration. By addressing the main freshwater ecosystems, large rivers, small streams, peatlands and wetlands in different European countries, the RSPs aim to serve as inspiration for restoration practitioners and policy makers and other key stakeholders throughout Europe.

To make sense of the complex and diverse contexts, the RSPs follow a common framework and answer questions regarding WHY, WHERE, WHAT, HOW and WHO on freshwater restoration. In understanding the WHY, the RSPs link to EU Green Deal goals, making the RSP goals holistic, science-based and policy-relevant. In terms of WHERE, the plans range from regional to national level. RSPs of Kvorning wetland rewetting DK and Blue Belt DE are ready-made national blueprints to be adapted elsewhere.

In terms of WHAT, RSPs identify a wide set of practical measures to be taken in the field, measures oriented towards policies and practices and measures related to public involvement. Some of these measures build on past experiences and are widely applied (e.g. fish passages, rewetting, workshops with stakeholders) but also more innovative approaches, such as use of leaky dams,

floodplain rewetting, citizen science and pub talks with farmers are used. Replication of these measures elsewhere is recommendable. However, it is essential that measures are targeted to suit local conditions and contexts otherwise measure effectiveness will be uncertain.

To build this kind of understanding, multidisciplinary teams with environmental, social and economic expertise are required. Furthermore, measure effectiveness (i.e. “what works”) can only be understood with adequate monitoring data from both biophysical and socio-economic systems. In this regard, the RSPs highlight the challenges related to implementing long-term monitoring, particularly in terms of funding. Without long-term systems monitoring, also options for corrective actions (i.e. adaptive management), become difficult.

The HOW question is answered through timeline and budget plans. Timelines are mostly only clearly described for short to medium term (2025-2035) for which the RSPs typically emphasize implementing diverse restoration measures. Long-term planning (2035 and beyond) is considered challenging due to uncertainties in the environment (e.g. climate change), policy and funding. The public sector has a dominant role as funder of restoration actions but steps towards attracting private sector finances are made. Overall, the restoration budgets vary greatly, as the details are presented per measure (e.g. price of rewetting per hectare), per unit of restoration (e.g. price of restored river km) or per project (e.g. total costs of project entailing multiple measures).

Stakeholder engagement is crucial for mainstreaming restoration into policies and practices and thus RSPs involve diverse public, private and civil society actors at national, regional and local levels. Co-creation of the RSPs by actors from these different sectors is essential for their wider acceptance. Visualization, such as infographics showing before and after restoration sites is helpful in communicating the RSP ideas to the wider public. However, given that stakeholders have different interests and power positions, the RSPs are also a forum to hear the less powerful voices, identify tensions and seek constructive solutions. In the RSPs, an example of these less powerful voices are local stakeholders typically engaged through local community associations. Constructive solutions are sought through

collaborative planning, education and public dialogue.

In the future, the RSPs will be implemented in several ways (WHO): in some RSPs, the RSP is “owned” by a specific actor (e.g., EmscherGenossenschaft in the Emscher basin restoration DE) or group of stakeholders (Kvorning wetland rewetting DK). However, in most cases, the aim is to incorporate the RSP into national or regional policy strategies and plans. Many RSPs emphasize that the document is supportive and inspiring for policymakers to address restoration more holistically, as the planning is based on holistic frameworks such as EU Green Deal goals and Nature-based Solutions.

This RSP synthesis highlights that one of the main challenges in mainstreaming restoration and upscaling is the lack of financial benefits, particularly viable income streams from restoration activities and implementation of Nature-based Solutions. If restored freshwater ecosystems with their biodiversity and ecosystem services are not seen as attractive land use, the private sector will not participate at the needed scale and pace. To attract landowners, RSPs highlight the need for public funding, the role of information in improving practices, as well as using local champions (e.g., big farmers) to showcase the benefits of restoration. Also, developing sustainable business models is highly needed.

In recent years, restoration has been a politically contested topic. The Regional Scalability Plans show that despite political and economic turmoil, co-creating ambitious restoration plans with key stakeholders is possible.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Why is freshwater ecosystem restoration and upscaling needed?

Europe's freshwater environment is in an alarming state, as our freshwater ecosystems are largely degraded, and threatened by biodiversity loss and water pollution. Climate change is further aggravating the situation and extreme weather events like floods and droughts are becoming increasingly common. In addition to hosting biodiversity, our freshwater ecosystems have high socio-economic importance, from the supply of clean water and food, buffering floods and droughts to provisioning recreation. Ecosystem degradation thus poses risks to economic development and human well-being, as agricultural production, transportation, trade, recreation and tourism are severely affected.

Agricultural expansion, urbanization and industrial development have led to massive changes in the European freshwater landscapes during the last centuries. European large and small rivers have been channelized and trained in the name of hydropower, water supply, flood protection and navigation. Peatlands and wetlands have been drained for agriculture, forestry as well as peat extraction. In water management, engineering approaches have prevailed as dikes, dams and channels have pierced floodplains and peatlands to make room for agricultural land, built environments and to ensure flood protection. In fact, the extent of floodplains has reduced by nearly 75 % (Globevnik et al. 2020). The building of river infrastructure, reduction of wetlands, and river alterations, including hydrological changes and loss of river connectivity, have had a drastic negative impact on freshwater biodiversity and water quality.

Implementing large-scale restoration of freshwater ecosystems through Nature-based Solutions has great potential for restoring both biodiversity and improving human benefits through enhancing the resilience of ecosystem services (European Commission, 2020). Although it is often no longer feasible to return ("restore") to the original state, urgent actions are needed to improve remaining ecosystems with regard to their structure and functioning to conserve and restore biodiversity and secure ecosystem services. Policy mandates for restoration have recently emerged and acceleration and upscaling of ecosystem restoration have been put forward by the most recent conference of parties of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 2022) and the recently adopted European Nature Restoration Law (European Union 2024). There are also supportive legal frameworks, such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD) that seek to reach good status for all of Europe's waters by 2027.

The restoration of rivers, lakes, wetlands and their catchments has a long tradition, dating back to the Ramsar Convention in the 1970s and beyond. Despite long tradition and legal frameworks (e.g., WFD), restoration measures have not significantly enhanced water quality or improved biodiversity. For example, 60% of water bodies are currently not reaching good ecological status (Johansson, 2023). This is because the restoration scale is often too small and narrowly focused; good initiatives are insufficiently replicated and restoration is not considered in other policy fields, such as agriculture and hydropower. Furthermore, restoration rarely has incorporated societal problem-solving. This means that restoration measures are not "owned" by key sectors, such as agriculture, water industry, forestry and energy, making them a niche activity for environmental and conservation regulatory agencies and funds. It must be also acknowledged that the (economic) activities of the aforementioned sectors have also contributed to ecosystem degradation.

Upscaling entails that restoration projects need to better embed the needs and concerns of other sectors (Arthington, 2021). Already currently, multiple linkages can be found, such as the need to mitigate and adapt to climate change. In Denmark and Finland, for example, this has resulted in increased interest in peatlands and how these landscapes are used and managed to reduce CO₂ emissions or even make them function as a carbon sink. Similarly, in Germany, the need for costly repairs of the waterborne transport infrastructure (e.g., locks and bridges) has opened opportunities for demolishing these as traffic amounts have significantly declined. In the Netherlands, policies call for making 'water and soil a guiding principle'¹ in spatial planning. Supporting and building nature-based services in these other domains is essential to look for opportunities to combine ecosystem restoration with climate adaptation planning at a landscape scale.

¹ <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/actueel/nieuws/2022/11/25/kabinet-maakt-water-en-bodem-sturend-bij-ruimtelijke-keuzes>

Common terms in freshwater ecosystem restoration

There is a myriad of terms being used in relation to ecosystem restoration and specific types of measures that can contribute to achieving these goals. The most important ones are mentioned in this glossary:

Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems that address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services, resilience and biodiversity benefits (UNEP/EA, 2022). Examples of Nature-based Solutions for freshwater are rewetting floodplains and reconnecting rivers, which improve water quality, capture carbon, provide habitat for wildlife, and reduce flood and drought risks.

Ecosystem Restoration aims to assist in the recovery of ecosystems that have been degraded or destroyed, as well as conserving the ecosystems that are still intact (UNEP 2021). Ecosystem Restoration measures can be Nature-based Solutions when they address both environmental and societal problems.

Natural Water Retention Measures (NWRM) are a specific kind of ecosystem restoration measure. These multifunctional measures aim to protect and manage water resources and address water-related challenges by restoring or maintaining ecosystems as well as natural features and characteristics of water bodies using natural means and processes. (Magnier et al. 2023)

1.2 Regional Scalability Plans

Landscape-level strategies help include mainstream ecosystem restoration and Nature-based Solutions in policies and practices. During the MERLIN project (2021-2025), the 17 MERLIN case studies have, together with their stakeholders, developed landscape-level strategies referred to here as Regional Scalability Plans (RSP). These Regional Scalability Plans (RSPs) extend freshwater-related restoration activities to a wider landscape and entail long-term planning. Regional Scalability Plans have a mid to long-term horizon (20 to 30 years) and take a larger regional perspective to mainstream ecosystem restoration and Nature-based Solutions. These plans typically have created a long-term vision for the region, involve multiple stakeholders, and link to multiple policy goals. In addition to biodiversity and climate policies, also economic and social policy goals have been in the spotlight in RSP development. In MERLIN, identifying and building linkages to the EU Green Deal goals has been particularly important. Furthermore, these plans include a list of supportive actions as well as estimates for budgets and timelines. In other words, these plans provide answers to five essential questions: WHY is large-scale restoration needed, WHERE the restoration actions take place, WHAT the work entails, HOW is the work organized and funded and WHO is involved and responsible for implementation.

Figure 1 The geographical positions of the MERLIN case studies (left). The case studies are grouped within three clusters: i) peatlands and wetlands (green), ii) small streams and basins (light blue) and iii) large transboundary rivers (dark blue). These case studies cover a wide range of freshwater ecosystems within a basin (catchment, watershed) (right)

1.3 Synthesis of MERLIN Regional Scalability Plans

This document synthesizes 16 MERLIN Regional Scalability Plans (RSPs) (Figure 1 and annex 7.1). The Bosnia case study (CS 6) RSP was not received in time (Deadline June 2024) for the final analysis. Furthermore, the MERLIN project added an additional case study halfway through the project, the Ervidel case study (CS 18-southern Portugal), which was exempted from RSP development. Within MERLIN, the case studies have been divided into three clusters: peatlands, small streams and basins and large transboundary rivers. The RSP synthesis results are mostly presented by clusters to highlight the commonalities and differences.

This deliverable explains the MERLIN approach for RSP development (Chapter 2). Chapter 3 provides an overview of RSPs, presenting the key features, goals and actions, and stakeholders involved. The upscaling actions are summarized for the three clusters: peatlands and wetlands, small streams and basins and large rivers (Chapter 4). The document provides reflections and suggestions on how this process of creating RSPs can be replicated and upscaled beyond this MERLIN initiative (Chapter 5). The individual RSPs are available as separate documents via the case study portal at the MERLIN website (<https://project-MERLIN.eu/cs-portal.html>).

1.4 What is upscaling?

Drawing on the innovation literature, the ability to expand and upscale (or scale-up) has emerged as an important attribute of successful and impactful initiatives and projects. The concept has become increasingly popular as it holds the promise of responding to the environmental, climate and social crises by expanding the scope and impact of good initiatives to regional, national and international levels. To ground our work theoretically, the MERLIN project has used two frameworks: The SUM framework in developing RSPs and the scaling out/up/deep framework to analyze the diverse dimensions of scalability.

For the RSP development, we have applied the **Scaling Up Management (SUM) framework** developed by Management Systems International (Management Systems International 2016) <https://www.msiworldwide.com/>. Drawing on the theories and practices of strategic management, their framework consists of a three-step approach and 10 tasks. More specifically, Step 1 is based on best practices related to strategic planning in complex settings; Step 2 focuses on political and change management functions associated with consensus building, policy change, and resource allocation; and Step 3 emphasizes the operational aspects of complex, multi-actor reform. The SUM Framework has been tested and applied by diverse actors in various settings, including governments, NGOs and the private sector in the fields of agriculture, food security, fish and wildlife conservation, climate change, resilience and livelihood enhancement. In addition to applications focused on scaling interventions that began at small scale outside of government, the SUM Framework has been applied to situations in which experimentation and scaling up were undertaken by governments or donors as part of a deliberate strategy of reform (Management Systems International 2016).

The **Scaling Out, Up, and Deep framework is applied to analyze** the diverse RSP scaling activities. This framework has been extensively applied in the literature (Moore, Riddell & Vocisano 2015; Salafsky et al 2021) to understand the different types of scaling:

- **Scaling out** answers the question ‘What is replicated?’ and entails that good and effective measures are replicated in wider geographical regions, such as in the larger watershed basin. For example, the Emscher basin restoration DE will replicate and expand flowering measures in the wider catchment. In addition to restoration measures, also measures related to policies and societal engagement, such as thematic workshops with stakeholders can be scaled out.
- **Scaling up** answers the question ‘how are policies or practices changed?’. This entails that restoration projects can support or change policies and institutions so that the policy context is supportive and enables long-term restoration. The scaling up measures can provide new information for policymakers, pilot new approaches, build new networks and strengthen collaboration among policy actors. These measures target not only practices but also changes in laws, regulations and rules. In the MERLIN project, scaling up has also entailed building explicit linkages to the EU Green Deal goals and thus the strategies and actions of the RSPs are connected to multiple policy goals at the same time.
- **Scaling deep** answers the question ‘how are underlying values and attitudes changed?’. Transformative change is not possible without scaling deep and this work consists of work that affects people’s hearts and minds. Often education and raising awareness are a start for scaling deep. Also opportunities to participate and interact with others (in a respectful manner) are avenues for change.

2 Regional Scalability Plans to upscale freshwater ecosystem restoration

This chapter explains the approach taken in the MERLIN project to create the Regional Scalability Plans for each of the MERLIN case studies. The MERLIN approach to creating Regional Scalability Plans was a carefully designed multi-step development process underlined by stakeholder engagement. Stakeholder engagement is crucial. In addition to government and public bodies, also companies, farmers, non-governmental organisations, and local community associations have been involved. In many cases, the need to develop an RSP has helped to bring together a diverse set of stakeholders to discuss regional development, nature-society relationships, and the future of freshwater ecosystem restoration. The development of RSP enabled stakeholders to create shared visions for future developments and to think holistically to achieve multiple Green Deal goals. Each case study organized several workshops during the RSP development that enabled both consultation but also knowledge co-production so that diverse views and values could be taken into account (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Examples of events with external stakeholder interaction (Top left: Danube floodplain restoration Austria, right Tisza floodplain rewetting Hungary, bottom left Room for the Rhine Netherlands, right Tzipori basin restoration Israel)

Table 1 presents an overview of the case studies that prepared RSPs and how they were created. Each case study had its approach and ways to engage stakeholders depending on pre-existing connections and processes. Some case studies were able to link RSP development to other ongoing initiatives. For example, in the Danube floodplain reconnect RO, the EU Horizon Project REXUS provided guidance for dialogues on the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems nexus challenges in the area, taking a wider approach to management of the area, but with closely related goals from the perspective of the lead partners. In the Lima floodplain forest restoration PT, a LIFE-project facilitated the ongoing process of onboarding and involving stakeholders and jointly working towards an overall improvement of the area.

Furthermore, in Kvorning wetland rewetting DK, Room for the Rhine NL, Blue Belt Germany DE, Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI, Tzipori basin restoration IL and Forth basin restoration UK, among others, ongoing integrated management policies, plans and initiatives of large areas at regional and national level, provided an excellent starting point for the RSP development as well as building policy support to connect RSP contributions to national efforts. At the same time, the RSPs provided an additional opportunity to reflect on these national efforts in a broader perspective making use of the interactions between the case studies during the cluster field visits in 2022 and 2023.

Table 1 Overview of the process with external parties per case study

No	Case study	Short description of RSP process	Detailed explanation
CS01	Kvorning wetland rewetting DK	Prepared by policy practitioners	The RSP is an attempt to best describe the Danish efforts of taking 100.000 hectares out of production in Denmark, and turning them back into wetlands, to reduce CO2 emissions. It describes the framework, criterias, stakeholders, compensations for landowners, etc. The RSP is written by Naturstyrelsen (The Danish Nature Agency) with input from Aarhus University and support Naturstyrelsens Headquarter.
CS02	Deba barrier removal ES	Prepared by researchers with the help of several consultations with stakeholders	The RSP has been prepared by the Group of Stream Ecology at the University of the Basque Country, based on the experience of working with the Sustainability Department (formerly Hydraulic Works) of the Gipuzkoa Provincial Council on the MERLIN project. At the same time, this RSP is also the result of the multiple inputs from other departments of the administration, as well as from stakeholders such as the insurance, hydropower sector and nature conservation NGOs.
CS03	Beaver river engineering SE	Prepared by researchers and practitioners with initial input from stakeholders	This document has been written by representatives of the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) and the Swedish Forest Agency (Skogsstyrelsen). At an early stage, feedback has been provided by the following organizations that are also part of the Swedish MERLIN reference group: County Administrative Board of Västerbotten, Sportfiskarna (NGO, Swedish Anglers Association), Sveaskog (forest enterprise), Södra (forest owner's association). However, for the content of this document the authors are fully responsible.
CS04	Room for the Rhine NL	Prepared by researchers and practitioners with the help of several consultations with stakeholders	Most of the groundwork was conducted by the Dutch MERLIN project team, consisting of RWS and Deltares colleagues, whereas input from a variety of PAGW colleagues and stakeholders from Provinces of Gelderland and Overijssel and waterboards, was gathered during several workshops in the period 2022-2024. As such this is the first version of this plan and it will be revised as needed during the MERLIN project and beyond.
CS05	Kampinos wetland rewetting PL	Prepared by policy practitioners (national park staff) in consultations with policy makers and researchers	The RSP was written by Kampinos National Park staff with the approval of the Park Director. During the process, members of the Case Study Board and Marshal's office were consulted.
CS06	Hutovo Blato peatland rewetting BIH	Not received in time	
CS07a	Danube floodplain restoration AT	Prepared by researchers with the help of several consultations with stakeholders	In the writing process, we consulted the national implementing partner viadonau and its stakeholder board, which has been doing restoration works at the Danube east of Vienna for the last 25 years, with an integrative approach. We also included experts from the above-mentioned ministries and partners from our twinning case study (LIFE IP IRIS) locally acting on other Austrian rivers and streams. Additionally, the Verbund AG – Austria's largest hydropower provider – was contacted to get insights on their restoration efforts at the Danube west of Vienna.
CS07b	Danube sidearm reconnect HU	Prepared by NGO practitioners with the help of researchers and policymakers	Most of the groundwork was conducted in close cooperation between WWF Hungary as implementation and the HUN-REN Balaton Limnological Research Institute as scientific partners in the MERLIN project. The RSP also benefited from several workshops where researchers, local and national policymakers and a variety of stakeholders discussed possibilities of restoration actions in the Hungarian stretch of the Danube.

No	Case study	Short description of RSP process	Detailed explanation
CS08	Danube floodplain reconnect RO	Prepared by NGO practitioners with the help of researchers	During the implementation of the MERLIN project, but also during other initiatives a large group of stakeholders have been consulted. The entire process of the engagement of the stakeholders has been done extensively recently under the EU Horizon project REXUS.
CS09	Tisza floodplain rewetting HU	Prepared by NGO practitioners with consultation with a large body of diverse stakeholders	<p>While writing the RSP, we drew on the experience gained during the fieldwork of the MERLIN project, the suggestions and inspiration given by the Case Study Board, local farmers at pilot sites, representatives of the Upper Tisza Regional Water Directorate, the Network of Village Advisers, the National Chamber of Agriculture and the Hortobagy National Park Directorate in the Bereg Pilot Site.</p> <p>In 2024, we held a series of workshops on the planning of a Tisza Valley Strategy with key leaders, planners, and researchers in the Hungarian water sector, representatives of major NGOs working on sustainability, and experts of outstanding importance in agri-environmental research. Representatives participated in these meetings from the General Directorate of Water Management, VIZITERV Environ, Budapest University of Technology and Economics Department of Sanitary and Environmental Engineering, National Environmental Council, National Society of Conservationists, Association for Hungarians in the Carpathian Basin, Alliance for the Living Tisza and. We have incorporated the conclusions of this high-level, multi-sectoral series of discussions into the RSP. The description of most of the planned actions is a product of these discussions.</p>
CS10	Blue Belt Germany DE	Collaboratively by policy-makers, practitioners and researchers with consultation from stakeholders	<p>Most of the groundwork was conducted by diverse working groups within the Waterway and Shipping Administration (WSV) and in close collaboration with other federal authorities and agencies.</p> <p>The methodological approach to developing the Blue Belt program involved a systematic analysis of ecological, hydrological, and land use data for Germany's federal waterways. Initially, comprehensive assessments were conducted to identify deficiencies and restoration potentials. Following this, pilot projects were implemented as "ecological stepping stones" to test the feasibility of restoration measures and assess their outcomes. These projects aim to balance ecological goals with the needs of navigation and other waterway uses. Additionally, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are applied to measure the effectiveness of the interventions and incorporate the findings into future projects.</p>
CS11	Emscher basin restoration DE	Prepared by practitioners and researchers	The RSP was written by the water management association Emschergerossenschaft and researchers from University of Duisburg-Essen.
CS12	Lima floodplain forest restoration PT	Researchers and restoration practitioners, in collaboration with policymakers	<p>The plan was developed by MERLIN project investigators and the stakeholder council. It was discussed in several meetings aimed at local political decision-makers. Having launched the challenge of developing a regional scalability plan, we brought together technicians and managers to prepare a proposal.</p> <p>The area was delineated, considering opportunities and limitations, a map was submitted for approval to the Protected Area Management Committee. After approval of this proposal, preliminary project work began, presenting and discussing ideas, plans and concrete actions. Through a survey and the draft plan, people and entities that they consider important were invited to make contributions to improve the project. A workshop was held with interested parties where the RSP was presented. This was followed by the delivery of the draft, which, after review, became RSP.</p>

No	Case study	Short description of RSP process	Detailed explanation
CS13	Sorraia river restoration PT	Researchers, practitioners and policymakers, with consultation from stakeholders	The RSP targeted the Restoration of Mediterranean lowland River Landscapes (ReMiLes) and was written in cooperation with the High Authority for Irrigation. We had input from Farmers Associations, companies involved in restoration actions, from two municipalities and from individual farmers.
CS14	Kompassuo peatland rewetting FI	Researchers and practitioners with initial feedback from stakeholders	The RSP was written by researchers from the Finnish Environment Institute and experts of Tapio, a government-owned company providing forestry, restoration and sustainability services. During the RSP development, diverse stakeholders were consulted to collect their ideas and suggestions.
CS15	Tzipori basin restoration IL	Researchers and policymakers, with consultation from stakeholders	A joint effort between the Kishion Drainage Authority, The Steinhardt Natural History Museum at Tel Aviv University and 'AGMA' a national non-profit organization for the dissemination of professional knowledge in stream rehabilitation.
CS16	Upper Scheldt restoration BE	Researchers and policymakers, with consultation from stakeholders	The RSP was developed via a workshop in consultation with various authorities and stakeholders such as the representatives from the Institute of Nature and Forest, Flanders Environmental Agency, Province of East-Flanders (Department of Agriculture, Department of Environment and Nature), Flemish Land Agency, Commune of Oudenaarde, Provinciaal Centrum voor Milieuonderzoek – Erosion Coordinator, Farmers, Algemeen Boerensyndicaat and Regionaal Landschap Vlaamse Ardennen.
CS17	Forth basin restoration UK	Collaborative partnerships between diverse stakeholders	Plan was written by a cohesive partnership between stakeholders such as Local Authorities, Land Managers and Local Communities, Government Bodies and Non-Government Organisations in the Forth Region.

2.1 The multi-step process of RSP development

Successful upscaling requires a good and thorough understanding of the current approaches to restoration as well as the socio-political context. This is essential to ensure that upscaling succeeds and effective measures are taken forward. The MERLIN project applied a multi-step approach to upscaling that also included the use of multiple strategic planning tools. Figure 3 presents the process, and it consists of

- 1) Case studies examined how their project contributes to EU Green Deal goals and how to strengthen the contributions. The case studies identified the primary and secondary Green Deal goals relevant to their situation.
- 2) Case studies evaluated their projects using the IUCN Self-Assessment Tool on Nature-based Solutions (IUCN 2024). The tool helps to identify to what extent their project meets the standards of the IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions. The projects also identified ways to improve their scores.
- 3) Using the insight gained in 1 & 2, the case studies conducted a multi-perspective gap analysis using a Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis in collaboration with selected stakeholders. This analysis enabled the case studies to improve, optimize and prioritize measures and these were published as optimization strategies (Buijse et al., 2022). Optimization has been crucial to ensuring that scaling is not only about scaling out individual measures but that synergistic linkages are built in terms of measures and policy goals (scaling up).
- 4) Drawing on these resources, the case studies were well prepared to start developing initial RSPs. Using a guiding template, the case studies compiled an initial plan. These initial plans and their synthesis were published in “Interim Regional Scalability Plans” (Pietilä et al. 2023). Before starting the finalization of regional scalability plans, the case studies received feedback and suggestions for improvements on their interim plans from MERLIN restoration, stakeholder and policy engagement and funding experts.
- 5) The development of final scalability plans was guided by a planning framework (Annex 7.2), which included various meetings both online and in-person to support RSP development and enable collective

learning among case studies. Furthermore, a self-assessment of upscaling (Chapter 2,2) was considered particularly helpful. In addition, the diverse stakeholder engagement activities shaped the goals and content of the plans, such that the final plans have a broader scope in terms Green Deal goals compared to the original plans.

Figure 3 The route map towards final regional scalability plan for each case study. The SWOT and optimisation strategies have been intermediate steps making use of the IUCN self-assessment for nature-based solutions and the European Green Deal goals.7.2

2.2 Self-assessment of the current status of upscaling

The interim RSPs of the case studies (Pietilä et al. 2023) revealed that there were substantial differences in the RSPs, particularly in terms of the maturity of the plan. Most case studies were focused on planning the upscaling process. However, some of the case studies (e.g., Kvorning wetland rewetting DK and Blue Belt Germany DE) were already implementing the upscaling plan. To support the case studies in building successful upscaling processes, a self-assessment framework was developed. Building on the upscaling process of Management systems international, the coordination team (Ojanen, Buijse and Penning) created a framework to assist the case studies to understand their position, the steps achieved and the steps ahead. All the case studies were asked to self-assess the current status of their upscaling for 11 tasks, which are essential for successful upscaling. Each task was assessed using a 5-point scale: i) task is ready, ii) (case study has) advanced or concrete ideas, iii) (case study has) initial vague or generic thoughts, iv) not relevant to the case study and v) do not know how to do this. The results of this self-assessment for each case study are shown in Figure 4.

The current status and approaches to scaling up varied from being ready with all tasks for the Danish case study (Kvorning wetland rewetting DK) to the Portuguese case study (Lima floodplain forest restoration PT) for which there were only initial thoughts for some tasks. The case studies were most advanced with tasks 1, 'Checking the 'what, why, how and where', 2, 'Evaluating and increasing the ambition of the plan', and 4, 'Understanding stakeholder needs', for which the majority felt they were ready or had advanced and concrete ideas. The tasks for which most case studies had only initial vague or no ideas were 7, 'Identifying information gaps', 8, 'Mobilizing resources: identifying human and financial resources needed to support the scale-up process', 10, 'Coordinating action' and 11, 'Adjusting strategy and maintaining momentum'. In only a few cases

was a single task considered irrelevant. This shows the importance of each of these tasks to the upscaling process.

The status review of all the case studies also guided the case studies to ask each other for support. During an RSP development support session in January 2024, the case studies expressed appreciation for the self-assessment because it made them reflect on where they currently stand and supported learning.

Cluster	Peatlands & wetlands						Small stream and basins						Large rivers						
	1	3	5	6	12	14	2	11	13	15	16	17	4	7a	7b	8	9	10	
Case study number	1	3	5	6	12	14	2	11	13	15	16	17	4	7a	7b	8	9	10	
Case study name	Kvorning	Beaver introduction	Kampinos	Hutovo Blato	Lima	Kompassuo	Deba	Emscher	Sorraia	Tzipori	Upper Scheidt	Forth	Rhine NL	Danube AT	Danube HU	Danube RO	Trisa	Blue Belt D	
STEP 1: Reviewing existing plans																			
Task 1: Checking the what, why, how and where	RE	AI	AI	VT	VT	RE	RE	AI	AI	AI	AI	AI	AI	AI	AI	AI	AI	AI	RE
Task 2: Evaluate and increase the ambition of the plan	RE	AI	VT	VT	VT	AI	RE	AI	VT	AI	AI	AI	AI	AI	AI	VT	AI	AI	
Task 3: Provide more details and specificity to the plan: actions and ownership and funding	RE	VT	AI	NI	NI	VT	RE	AI	VT	AI	VT	AI	VT	AI	VT	VT	VT	AI	
STEP 2: Strengthen the preconditions for scaling-up																			
Task 4: Understanding stakeholder needs	RE	RE	AI	AI	NI	RE	AI	VT	AI	RE	VT	AI	AI	AI	VT	VT	VT	VT	
Task 5: Legitimizing change	RE	AI	VT	AI	VT	AI	AI	NI	AI	AI	AI	VT	AI	AI	VT	VT	VT	AI	
Task 6: Building constituency	RE	AI	VT	AI	VT	AI	AI	AI	NI	VT	VT	AI	VT	AI	VT	VT	VT	RE	
Task 7: Identifying information gaps	RE	AI	AI	AI	VT	VT	VT	AI	VT	VT	VT	VT	VT	AI	VT	VT	VT	VT	
STEP 3: Implementing the scaling up: managing the change and adapting as necessary.																			
Task 8: Mobilize resources: identifying human and financial resources necessary to support the scaling up process	RE	AI	AI	VT	NI	VT	AI	NI	NI	VT	VT	AI	VT	AI	VT	VT	VT	VT	
Task 9: Modify and strengthen organizations: developing and executing institutional capacity-building and organizational development plans for major participants	RE	AI	AI	VT	NI	VT	VT	AI	NI	VT	NR	AI	VT	RE	NK	NR	VT	RE	
Task 10: Coordinate action	RE	AI	NI	VT	NI	VT	VT	NI	NI	VT	VT	AI	VT	RE	VT	VT	VT	NI	
Task 11: Adapt Strategy and maintain momentum	RE	VT	NI	NI	NI	VT	NI	NI	NI	VT	VT	VT	AI	RE	NI	NI	VT	AI	
Legend																			
	RE	This is ready																	
	AI	Advanced and concrete ideas																	
	VT	First vague / generic thoughts																	
	NI	No idea yet																	
	NR	Not relevant for our CS																	
	NK	Don't know how to do this																	

Figure 4 Results of the self-assessment of the status (end of 2023) of upscaling of all MERLIN case studies.

3 Overview of Regional Scalability Plans

RSPs follow the same general outline using a framework consisting of WHY, WHERE, HOW, WHAT, and WHO questions used during RSP development (Pietilä et al., 2023). The plans identify the following features

- **WHY:** Explains the rationale for the RSP, including identification of main environmental, economic, and social problems and potential solutions. See Chapter 3.2 for more information.
- **WHERE:** Identification of the region and areas that the RSP targets, typically, a watershed basin. See Chapter 3.3 for more information.
- **HOW:** Explains budget and timeline and how the plans are taken forward. See Chapter 3.4.
- **WHAT:** Presents detailed policy goals (including Green Deal goals) and actions. See Chapter 3.4.
- **WHO:** Description of stakeholders that are or will be involved in the upscaling. See Chapters 3.5 and 3.7.
- In addition, the RSPs discuss uncertainties and boundary conditions and how these may affect the plans. See Chapter 5.2.

3.1 The key features of the RSPs

Table 2 summarizes the key features of each RSP. These include the case study name and RSP plan name; objectives of the RSP (WHY?), the RSP region (WHERE?); likely funding and timeline (HOW?), and RSP plan owners/managers or role in the larger policy context (WHO?). Questions related to policy goals and actions (WHAT?) and actors (WHO?) are presented in the following chapters (3.5-3.7) as well. The information presented in Table 2 is drawn from the individual RSPs. However, some clarifications and input to the table were received via personal communication with the case study leads.

Table 2 Overview of the focus and key features of the individual RSPs.

Case Study	RSP name	Objectives of the RSP (Why?)	Region (Where?)	Funding and timeline (How?)	RSP owner or role in larger policy context (Who?)
Kvorning wetland rewetting DK	Taking carbon-rich lowland soils out of production in Denmark.	Focus on describing the Danish national scheme related to green transition within agriculture. The aim of the RSP is to share this approach with international audiences to show the transition of the Danish agricultural sector to reduce CO2 emissions by taking 100.000 hectares of carbon-rich soils and adjacent areas out of production, by re-wetting the areas and thus support peatland restoration in Denmark	Nationally, focused on Jutland, Funen and Zealand, where the majority of the carbon-rich soils are found	Actions are currently funded by national government schemes until 2030, with a budget of currently 535 million euros* reserved for land purchases, compensations for landowners and restoration *For 2025 the ambitions are raised to take out 140.000 hectares and thus more funding will be allocated	The RSP describes the implementation of an ongoing government policy (approved in October 2021) by the Danish Nature Agency and the Danish Environmental Protection Agency
Deba barrier removal ES		To provide a framework to guide the improvement of the longitudinal connectivity of fluvial ecosystems to face climate change in accordance with the European Green Deals and Sustainable Development Objectives. Improvement is focused on the demolition of weirs (total or partial demolition). Additionally, RSP is to serve as an example of how to address conflicts related to weir removal and to provide an overview of the benefits and trade-offs of obstacle removal	The Basque country, covering an area of 7300 km2 and including 147 streams with approximately 7000 obstacles in them	Budget not stated, proposition to get funding through public tax, EU funding and other sources Obstacle removal plan creation (2025-2028), obstacle removal (2029-2044), monitoring (2029-2050), stakeholder engagement (2025-2050)	No institutional owner, however linkages to ongoing policy developments, such as the master plan for river obstacle removal of the Basque Water Agency and Master Plan for river management of Gipuzkoa Provincial Council All the relevant stakeholders should be involved in dissemination

Case Study	RSP name	Objectives of the RSP (Why?)	Region (Where?)	Funding and timeline (How?)	RSP owner or role in larger policy context (Who?)
Beaver river engineering SE	Beavers here and there, but not everywhere	To maximize the positive effects of beavers, and minimizing and mitigating the negative ones	Whole of Sweden, areas where beavers currently live and areas where they could live	<p>Beaver dam removal and building related cost are 500-5000€ per dam</p> <p>Other costs relate to communication and building digital tools (70 000€)</p> <p>Short term: Knowledge synthesis and dissemination in diverse topic</p> <p>Medium to long-term: reassessment of evidence-base and dissemination</p>	No institutional owner of the RSP, but linkages to existing policies, such the long-term goal of Swedish Forestry agency to rewet 100 000 ha of ditched peat-covered forest land by 2045. Currently, there is not enough clarity on beaver management-related responsibilities in Sweden.
Room for the Rhine NL	Rhine Reimagined: A Future-Forward Plan for Nature-Based Management	To foster an ecologically vibrant and resilient river ecosystem and expanding the space for nature's processes to occur naturally by enhancing hydrodynamic activity within floodplains of the Rhine.	Dutch Rhine branches covering the three branches— the Waal (including the Biesbosch area), the Nederrijn-Lek (unto Hagestein), and the IJssel— before entering the Lake IJsselmeer. This includes parts of the provinces Gelderland, Overijssel, Utrecht and Zuid Holland.	<p>Short to medium term (->2035) identification of relevant projects, policy and community of practice development and co-creation of monitoring plans with stakeholders</p> <p>Medium- to long-term (2035->): policy and community of practice development</p> <p>Funding: implementation as part of existing processes, EU and national initiatives and private funds such as mining companies and charity lottery (Postcode Loterij)</p>	Government agency Rijkswaterstaat and linkages to programs such as Dutch Programmatic Approach Large Waters (PAGW) and Dutch Integrated River Management program (IRM)
Kampinos wetland rewetting PL	Flowing Mazovia	To improve the conservation status of wetlands in Mazovia . The RSP presents an action plan for improving the hydrological conditions in the region through the transfer of knowledge and experience	From the Kampinos national park (385 km ²) to national park buffer zone (378 km ²) and to the wider Mazovia Province (35 597 km ²) in Central Poland	<p>Funding comes from each stakeholder for their own activities, from budgets, revenue from national park (e.g., permits, UNESCO grants)</p> <p>Until 2030: implementation of restoration projects, policy development</p> <p>Continuous: applying funding, awareness raising, multi-stakeholder collaboration</p>	<p>Different stakeholders will take the plan forward: Kampinos national park in its area,</p> <p>In the buffer zone, 8 municipalities and 3 counties</p> <p>The Marshal's office of the Mazowieckie Voivodeship will take more strategic role as well as promote public awareness on wetlands</p>

Case Study	RSP name	Objectives of the RSP (Why?)	Region (Where?)	Funding and timeline (How?)	RSP owner or role in larger policy context (Who?)
Hutovo Blato peatland rewetted BiH	Not received in time for the RSP synthesis				
Danube floodplain restoration AT	Future Danube plan	<p>Climate resilient, habitat and species rich Danube including all stakeholders and providing recreational space for all.</p> <p>To support decision-makers towards developing management plans to support a holistic approach for freshwater ecosystem restoration at the Austrian Danube on a large scale</p>	Measures implemented at the Danube east and west of Vienna are scaled up and adapted for revitalizing the whole Austrian Danube stretch from the German border to the border with Slovakia	<p>Rough estimate of 1 km of river costs 1 million euro</p> <p>The overall budget consists of existing projects (e.g., LIFE+ Traisen 30 million €) and fish passes ranging from 1,6 km to 14,2 km and budgets of 2,5 million to 12 million euro</p> <p>Funding comes from hydropower, federal government, EU and local communities and fishing associations</p> <p>Short-medium term (->2034): building a comprehensive river restoration strategy and identifying additional restoration measures, applying for funding, implementation, monitoring</p> <p>medium-long term: Seeking funding, implementation, monitoring</p> <p>Continuous: involve society</p>	No institutional owner, RSP will be integrated in national strategies and management activities

Case Study	RSP name	Objectives of the RSP (Why?)	Region (Where?)	Funding and timeline (How?)	RSP owner or role in larger policy context (Who?)
Danube sidearm reconnect HU	Scaling Up - From Vision to Large-Scale Change: The future's Danube	To promote sustainable water and landscape management through enhancing cooperation among stakeholders, building political support and increasing public engagement	Lower Hungarian stretch of the River Danube	<p>Three key measures are planned until 2030 (organizing stakeholder meetings, promoting sustainable water management, developing and implementing monitoring program), followed by 3 mid-term activities until 2037 that relate to restoration, governance and economic development</p> <p>Budget for stakeholder engagement and promotion communication < 80 000€/ year</p> <p>Restoration costs up to 1 mio €</p> <p>Governance and policy development 80 000- 400 000 €</p>	No institutional owner, but the work continues to highlight the importance of the issue and bring restoration into mainstream policies
Danube floodplain reconnect RO	Lower Danube Floodplain - an area of welfare	presents a vision of wise land use management for the Lower Danube floodplain , taking into account the needs of local communities. The plan aims to identify common actions to create a resilient Danube floodplain to climate change	RSP is focused on the Danube stretch from Iron Gates to Hârsova, covering 3869 km ²	<p>The budget will be estimated at the next stages. In previous projects on renaturalization and reconstruction, budgets have been estimated at 40-50 mio €</p> <p>Timeline considered until 2050</p> <p>Timeline for diverse activities (e.g., climate, drought resilience, and health and wellbeing) where some of the work is foreseen as continuous (e.g., collaboration with stakeholders) while others have clearer short-term scope (e.g., conducting studies on health impacts)</p>	The RSP aims to sustain and broaden the efforts of other restoration projects, such as Restore4Life, Danube4All and Dalia.

Case Study	RSP name	Objectives of the RSP (Why?)	Region (Where?)	Funding and timeline (How?)	RSP owner or role in larger policy context (Who?)
Tisza floodplain rewetting HU	Developing sustainable water management and landscapes in the Tisza Plain - Roadmap to 2050	<p>Preserve and develop natural flood plains through promotion of natural water retention measures (NWRM)</p> <p>Introduction of water retention-based, nature friendly, sustainable floodplain management in 150 000 hectares</p> <p>Improve livelihoods and increase resilience to climate change</p>	Hungarian part of the Tisza catchment area, the Great Plain and the Homokhátság areas, which is referred to as the Tisza Plain (ca 40 400 km ²)	<p>Provides a comprehensive and detailed timeline and budget.</p> <p>Budget estimate for diverse measures, totaling 20 billion</p> <p>Timeline for diverse actions for all the measures under Green Deal goals</p>	<p>Not a specific owner, but RSP may be used as input for Tisza Valley Strategy being prepared by the government</p> <p>RSP presents a roadmap for cooperation that identifies relevant actors in the public sector, civil society and farmer context</p> <p>Potentially, a network of local, regional and national organizations could take up some of the work</p>
Blue Belt Germany DE	<p>Germany's Blue Belt</p> <p>A model for Waterway Restoration and Sustainable Regional Development</p>	<p>Delivers insights from the national Blue Belt program to be shared with international audiences</p> <p>Blue Belt program enhances the ecological, social, and economic value of the country's waterways by 2050</p> <p>It focuses on restoring federal waterways and surrounding floodplains and transforms underutilized waterways into vibrant natural spaces, boosting regional development, biodiversity, and recreational opportunities</p>	The inland waterways of Germany, focused on particularly secondary waterways which handle lower freight traffic volumes. Selected sites must meet specific criteria to ensure they match with program goals	The program is set to run until 2050, with an estimated annual budget of € 50 million for river restoration and € 12-15 million for floodplain and wetland restoration . The total budget is estimated to be € 15 billion	Existing policy initiative which aligns and supports other strategies and plans, including national water strategy and national biodiversity strategy

Case Study	RSP name	Objectives of the RSP (Why?)	Region (Where?)	Funding and timeline (How?)	RSP owner or role in larger policy context (Who?)
Emscher basin restoration DE	Emscher- MERLIN Vision 2050	<p>By 2050, the majority of EGLV's green spaces will feature diverse, flowering meadows, thereby boosting biodiversity</p> <p>local population will utilize these biodiverse spaces and participate in their conservation, fostering greater environmental awareness. Enhanced landscapes lead to a richer nature experience and higher quality of life, strengthening mental health and serving as a health precaution</p>	Emscher and Lippe river basins, connecting to river Rhine in Ruhr area	<p>The timeline presented until 2050, covering two measures: establishment of flowering meadows and citizen science.</p> <p>Funding is discussed in terms of sources and EGLV responsibilities, added costs of environmentally friendly land management practices as well as costs of citizen science</p>	<p>The Emschergenossenschaft/Lippeverband (EGLV), which is Germany's largest water management association</p> <p>RSP links with strategies, plans and visions of the EGLV</p>
Lima floodplain forest restoration PT	'Ponte de Lima - Alto Minho's Lung'	Presents a work guide for stakeholders and others; improves understanding on the scaling-up process and the activities therein, clarifies responsibilities	Estorãos hydrographic basin, within the Protected Area limits, and the Lima River Special Area of Conservation, within the Ponte de Lima municipality limits.	Timeline proposed until 2050, with measures e.g. related to invasive species control, planting forests, river restoration and monitoring	<p>Not clearly defined, but target audience is defined:</p> <p>RSP is for public administration, like Alto Minho municipalities community (CIM Alto Minho), private companies and landowners</p>
Sorraia river restoration PT	Restoration of Mediterranean lowland River Landscapes ReMiles	<p>1) The restoration of Mediterranean lowland River Landscapes</p> <p>2) Support better management of rivers and include riparian rehabilitation, river restoration and invasive plant control, in addition to biodiversity promotion in the river areas.</p>	Irrigated areas and lowland river valleys of the Sorraia river basin	<p>Funding costs are considered until 2030, with a total budget of ca. 12 million euros.</p> <p>Timeline considered until 2050</p> <p>Timeline for diverse activities (e.g., climate, biodiversity and inclusivity) where some of the work is foreseen as continuous (e.g., removing invasive species) while other has clearer short-term scope (e.g., implementing natural filtration systems).</p>	RSP should be taken forward by Water and Agricultural authorities and managers of Mediterranean irrigated floodplains of Sorraia

Case Study	RSP name	Objectives of the RSP (Why?)	Region (Where?)	Funding and timeline (How?)	RSP owner or role in larger policy context (Who?)
Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI	Mainstreaming nature-based services in post-peat extraction areas	Supports holistic restoration planning in former peat extraction sites so that planning considers multiple impacts, including biodiversity, GHG emissions and water quality.	Focuses on peat-dominant landscapes in Northern Finland, such as those in the Oulujoki-Iijoki river basin (where case study Komppasuo is located)	Timeline covered until 2027 (through EU Just transition fund) Just transition fund is used as a funding source and further funding sources will be sought in the future (action item in the plan) Costs presented to selected restoration measures , in the case of wetlands, constructions and reintroduction of wetland vegetation, the costs range 500-10 000€/ha	No specific owner, but RSP informs regional and local planning, which is facilitated by existing and future networks
Tzipori basin restoration IL	The national restoration project of Tzipori stream	To revitalize the natural environment surrounding the Tzipori Stream in Israel. To restore and preserve the stream's ecosystem, enhancing biodiversity and water quality through sustainable management practices. To collaborate with local communities and environmental organizations to protect the stream's cultural and ecological significance while promoting recreational opportunities and educational programs for visitors and residents alike.	Tzipori stream and surroundings, considering the geographical and hydrological factors in the Kishon watershed	Actions are taken during 2023-2026. Specific milestones are stated, e.g., restoration at least one central tributary of the Tzipori stream by the end of 2025 A total budget for activities until 2026 is estimated at 40 million €	RSP is a summary of the actions in the Tzipori watershed rehabilitation master plan , covering years 2023-2026 Case study is planning how to continue the project beyond 2026

Case Study	RSP name	Objectives of the RSP (Why?)	Region (Where?)	Funding and timeline (How?)	RSP owner or role in larger policy context (Who?)
Upper Scheldt restoration BE	Restoring water quality and landscapes in the Flemish Ardennes to let them flourish!	Presents steps in enhancing water quality and biodiversity as well as a roadmap to address diffuse pollution	Flemish Ardennes, which includes the municipalities of Brakel, Zwalm, Zottegem, Oudenaarde and Maarkedal	Government and NGOs are funding sources, and further funding sources will be sought in the future (action item in the plan) A specific timetable is presented with measures first addressing funding and improving plans, followed by restoration and monitoring work.	No specific owner, but the province of East Flanders and the Landscape Park of the Flemish Ardennes will be the main driving forces of the RSP Furthermore, the RSP is a guidance document for local and regional authorities, policymakers and politicians Linkages to ongoing and planned policy initiatives, such as the Landscape Park Flemish Ardennes master plan
Forth basin restoration UK	2050 Scalability plan for River and Peatland restoration in the Forth Catchment.	enable landscape-scale change in terms of works to improve biodiversity, natural flood management and climate resilience across the rivers and peatland in the Forth region , while allowing stakeholders the means to live, work and thrive on the land	Forth catchment in the Eastern half of Central Scotland	A detailed timetable per goal and measure is presented, with the time horizon of 2050 Presents an overview of possible public funding sources, including available grant sums and support per measure (e.g., Peatland action program, Facility for Investment Ready Nature and agri-environmental and climate schemes). Peatland Code UK, a certification scheme supports commercialization of carbon benefits from restoration projects	Nature Scot and Forth River Trust will take the plan forward

3.2 Observations regarding the objectives of RSPs (WHY?)

All the case studies are working to restore freshwater ecosystems, but their RSPs have different focus points depending on the addressed problems and policy context. Also, the initial starting point, the type of MERLIN restoration project and the experience of the case study experts have influenced the RSP planning (see their self-assessments in Chapter 2.2). Some of the RSPs are very broad in terms of what kind of environmental, social and economic problems are addressed, which stakeholders are engaged and what kind of action is planned (e.g., Danube floodplain restoration AT, Danube sidearm reconnect HU, Tzipori basin restoration IL, Forth basin restoration UK) while other RSPs are more focused around single policy issues such as beaver management (Beaver river engineering SE) and restoration policies of peatlands (Kvorning wetland rewetting DK, Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI). Although these single policy issue RSPs (Sweden, Finland, Denmark) represent **the peatland cluster group**, the other RSPs in the peatlands cluster entailed broad problem focus and activities (Kampinos wetland rewetting PL, Forth basin restoration UK).

Sharing of experiences, knowledge and best practices is a key objective in those RSPs with a mature level of upscaling (Kvorning wetland rewetting DK, Blue Belt Germany DE) so that new audiences can learn about their restoration and upscaling work. Also, for Deba barrier removal ES, sharing best practices is important, as they are forerunners in addressing conflicts related to barrier removals. Overall, knowledge sharing plays a vital role in all RSPs. **Many RSPs emphasize that their plans have an important role in serving as a guide or framework on how to advance restoration planning in a holistic manner** (e.g., Deba barrier removal ES, Kampinos wetland rewetting PL, Danube floodplain restoration AT, Lima floodplain forest restoration PT, Sorraia river restoration PT, Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI). Furthermore, some RSPs provide a common vision that can guide these policies and plans (e.g., Danube floodplain reconnect RO, Tisza floodplain rewetting HU, Blue Belt DE, Emscher basin restoration DE, Forth basin restoration UK).

In the small streams and basins, the need to address the multiple pressures facing the river environment and ecosystems is highlighted. The multiple pressures result in a complex chain of interlinkages between environmental, climate and water problems, and thus, these RSPs have taken a very holistic planning approach, and the plans entail diverse restoration measures. For example, in the Sorraia river restoration PT, water scarcity and nutrient run-off is a specific core problem that is combined with challenges related to invasive species management and questions related to greenhouse gas emissions from irrigated floodplains. In the Upper Scheldt restoration BE, the combination of infrastructural changes to the landscape (weirs, channelization), high chemical pressures due to run-off from fields and limited sewage systems in rural areas have led to severe water pollution in the river. The RSP aims for river resilience so that diverse and diffuse sources of pollution are addressed and flood and drought risks are mitigated.

In terms of large rivers, flood risk reduction and navigation goals have traditionally played a prominent role in planning objectives. Many floodplains of large rivers have experienced serious droughts due to the combination of more extreme weather conditions, reduced flooding frequencies and lowered groundwater tables caused by incised river beds draining floodplains during low discharge periods. RSPs in this cluster note the need to **improve drought resilience** both for nature and society, particularly farming in the floodplains. Furthermore, addressing the negative impacts of **river infrastructure** (dams, dikes, bank fixation) is important **for large rivers and**, to some extent, **for small streams and basins**. However, the ecosystem impacts (e.g., impeded fish migration, disconnected floodplains and shoreline fixation) created by this infrastructure cannot be easily undone.

Across all clusters, RSPs are tackling **multiple challenges in the wider policy-making context**, including a lack of collaboration and coordination across sectors, policies and actors. This work entails improving communication and building collaboration among various actors through seminars, workshops, roundtables and field trips. However, challenges occur when stakeholders have different values, interests and policy aims. Through identification of multiple benefits and stakeholder engagement, RSPs aim to make restoration interesting and appealing to different audiences. Nevertheless, some key stakeholders are challenging and lack interest in restoration (e.g., Kampinos wetland rewetting PL, Danube sidearm reconnect HU, Sorraia river restoration PT). Different values and ideas about future development can also lead to conflicts if stakeholders and members of the public oppose ecosystem restoration. This resistance has been most visible in the case of Deba barrier removal ES, where opposition to barrier removal is addressed in the RSP by highlighting the role of transparency and building public dialogue. Furthermore, restoration can also be a topic that brings together disagreeing groups, such as in the Tzipori basin restoration IL, where stream restoration involves different groups of citizens (both Jews and Arabs), improves community relations and thus promotes social peace.

3.3 Observations regarding the region (WHERE?)

The RSPs extend the scope and diversity of measures from the MERLIN restoration project site to the wider region. In choosing the wider area, hydrological, environmental as well as political (jurisdictional) boundaries were considered. For example, the RSPs focused on river restoration extend measures both upstream and downstream while also considering surrounding areas, such as floodplains and forests. The boundaries are also affected by municipality limits, for example, in the case of Lima floodplain forest restoration PT, where the RSP area is under the Ponte de Lima municipality. Some cases, however, emphasize different understanding of the region. For example, the Blue Belt Germany DE RSP covers similar types of rivers nationwide, so-called secondary waterways, that handle lower freight traffic volumes, while the Swedish Beaver river engineering RSP examines the suitability of beaver habitation nationwide (i.e., whole of Sweden). In the RSPs focused on the Danube (Danube sidearm reconnect HU and Danube floodplain reconnect RO) as well as Tisza floodplain rewetting HU, the region is both very long and wide, extending to the floodplain areas used for agriculture and forestry adjacent to rivers.

3.4 Observations regarding timelines and budgets (HOW?)

In the MERLIN approach, “How?” relates to the timing and funding of the activities. In terms of planned activities, most of the RSPs divide their activities between short- to medium-term (until 2034) and long-term (2035-2050) activities. The short- and medium-term plans are characterized by further planning, implementation of restoration measures, stakeholder engagement and policy development as well as awareness raising. Also, monitoring and seeking funding is emphasized. In the long term, similar activities continue. A notable exception is that in terms of restoration measures, in the long-term, there is a need for fewer measures as previously implemented measures, such as natural refiltration systems and reforestation, are in place and working (e.g., Sorraia river restoration PT). Three RSPs provided only short-term plans (Kvorning wetland rewetting DK, Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI, Tzipori basin restoration IL) as their RSPs were affected by changes in main funding sources (Denmark, Finland) or because of major on-going planning processes that will influence the RSP plans (Israel).

In terms of funding, the RSPs highlighted the dominant role of public funding coming from government actors, the EU² and international bodies (e.g., UNESCO). The public sources of funding are highly diverse and include, for example, restoration programs, grants and agri-environmental schemes. Public funding dominates, with many projects depending on EU programs like LIFE, Horizon 2020, and European Regional Development Funds. National and regional government funds also play crucial roles. Other sources of funds were from the private sector and civil society, including mining companies and fishing associations. Despite recognizing the need for long-term financial planning, most RSPs do not provide specific alternatives to public funding for covering the entire scope of the projects. Furthermore, there is a lack of long-term financial strategies that would cover full project costs. An expectation not addressed in the RSPs is the WFD cost recovery, which could become a potential source of funding.

Given the emphasis on public funding, there is only a modest interest in securing private sector funding. While RSPs generally offer a detailed mapping of stakeholders and their interests (see also 3.6), the collaboration remains currently limited in terms of finances and economics (such as developing business models based on Nature-based Solutions). In some cases, industry involvement in the restoration process is suggested to create jobs and utilize restoration byproducts (e.g., Emscher basin restoration DE, Upper Scheldt river restoration BE). Overall, there is awareness that diversifying funding sources is necessary as exclusive reliance on public funding may hinder upscaling and the long-term sustainability of the plans. Generally, this awareness has not yet resulted in concrete strategies and financial plans for the RSPs.

Budgeting measures turned out to be one of the most challenging parts of the RSP development. Only a few RSPs provided the total cost of measures and these RSPs were mostly linked to existing government programmes. In the case of Kvorning wetland rewetting DK, there was a budget of 535 million € and in the case of Blue Belt DE, there was a yearly budget of 15 million €. Instead, many RSPs provided cost-estimates of previous restoration projects (e.g., Danube floodplain reconnect RO), specific restoration measures (Beaver river engineering SE, Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI) or cost per restored kilometer (e.g., Danube floodplain restoration AT). The Forth basin restoration UK RSP includes an overview of the restoration funding context in Scotland and identifies possibilities therein for the RSP activities.

² The adoption of Nature Restoration Law was not yet certain during the RSP development, and thus explicit references to restoration funds are limited

3.5 Observations regarding RSP ownership (WHO)?

The scaling plans have different roles in terms of policy uptake. Although collaboration and knowledge production with stakeholders improve policy relevance, the implementation of these plans into practice and policy is not a straightforward task. Some RSPs have identified specific institutional owners who have the responsibility and suitable mandate to take the RSP forward. For example, the Room for the Rhine NL RSP is taken forward by the government agency Rijkswaterstaat, the Emscher basin restoration DE by the Emschergenossenschaft/Lippeverband (Germany’s largest water management association) and the Sorraia river restoration PT should be taken forward by government authorities related to water and agriculture. In other plans, the RSP is viewed to be integrated into existing or upcoming policy strategies and management plans (e.g., Deba barrier removal ES, Danube floodplain restoration AT, Beaver river engineering SE). The RSP can also have an important role in guiding future policy work towards more holistic and ambitious restoration policies (e.g., Danube floodplain reconnect RO, Tisza floodplain rewetting HU, Kompasuo peatland rewetting FI, Upper Scheldt restoration BE).

Our vision on an infographic:

Fig. 5: Various states of rivers from past century until future vision

Figure 5 Infographics in the various RSPs. Top left Danube Hungary: past, present and vision for the future (source: RSP CS07b Danube side arm reconnected HU). Top right: Artist impression of Tziori basin restoration (Source: RSP CS16 Tziori basin restoration IL). Bottom left: Emscher 2030 vision prepared in a participatory way (source: RSP CS11 Emscher basin restoration DE). Bottom right: 'Room for the Rhine': Ecological perspective for the Dutch large rivers 2050 (source: RSP CS04 Room for the Rhine NL).

3.6 Green Deal goals and proposed measures (WHAT)

The RSPs also identify the “WHAT” by identifying relevant Green Deal goals and propose actions and measures to reach these. These measures can be grouped into four categories: measures in the field and actions related to either the policy, research or social domain. The social domain covers public participation and citizen engagement (Table 3). The RSPs include all types of measures. The measures include both concrete measures (e.g., ecological restoration actions) as well as key principles (e.g., accessibility for tourism) for measure design.

Table 3 Green Deal goals, restoration measures and supporting actions in the policy, research and social domains in the RSPs

Case study	Green Deal goals	Measures in the field suggested to reach the goals	Policy domain actions (rules, regulations)	Research domain actions	Social domain actions
Kvorning wetland rewetting DK	Carbon sequestration Zero pollution; Reduction of nitrogen loss to the aquatic environment Biodiversity improvement	Land consolidation in carbon-rich areas, often in/around valleys and rewetting of cultivated/drained (agricultural) areas	Landowner participation is voluntary, and so the government offers compensation for rewetting and/or land consolidation or simply buying land	Thorough pre-investigations related to the feasibility and cost efficiency of the projects, including pre-investigations of protected nature, habitats, species, etc. related to environmental screening and -approval	Kitchen table talks with individual landowners to discuss the objectives and possibilities provided by the projects Including locals e.g., groups working with public access in the project areas, etc
Deba barrier removal ES	Primary goals: climate, biodiversity, flood risk, inclusivity for local communities Secondary goals: green growth, health and wellbeing, knowledge, zero pollution	Stream self-purification through habitat heterogeneity Permeability plans for barriers and obstacles to serve multiple goals	Regular meetings with mayors	Analyse greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions resulting from the presence of obstacles in river ecosystems to provide other prioritization criteria for obstacle removal Biological effect monitoring based on fish and macroinvertebrate communities Monitoring of stream water quality based on physicochemical parameters Flood damage modelling	Awareness campaigns communicating the multiple benefits of barrier removal Communication channel between experts and citizens Up-to-date, public information, e.g., through updating websites
Beaver river engineering SE	<i>Main goal:</i> Biodiversity enhancement, <i>Secondary goals:</i> climate regulation, flood and drought resilience, health and well-being, zero pollution	Sustainable management of beavers and their dams throughout Sweden Monitor dams for multiple goals through a well-designed long-term monitoring scheme	There is a need to clarify which Swedish authority or other organization should be responsible for beavers	Monitor GHG emissions in beaver systems of different types, as well as potential risks posed by transmitting vector disease Reassess beaver dam functioning on longer terms	Disseminate knowledge of beaver dams and their management

Case study	Green Deal goals	Measures in the field suggested to reach the goals	Policy domain actions (rules, regulations)	Research domain actions	Social domain actions
Room for the Rhine NL	<p>Primary goals: Biodiversity net gain, Health and wellbeing, Inclusive participation and governance, Climate regulation</p> <p>Secondary goals: Drought resilience, sustainable food systems and land use, flood resilience, sustainable transport, zero pollution, financing the transition</p>	<p>Change land use from intensive agriculture to nature or organic farming</p> <p>Rewet floodplains</p> <p>Building a knowledge base: assess the benefits for the different goals through monitoring</p>	<p>Prepare an overarching restoration plan with key stakeholders</p> <p>Embed the RSP in follow-up projects (e.g., ResiRivers) and regional initiatives (Rivierklimaatpark IJsselpoort)</p> <p>Embed in national and regional policies (not further specified)</p> <p>Upscaling to other large rivers (Meuse)</p> <p>Streamline public funding to apply NbS</p>	<p>Creating a comprehensive, long-term monitoring plan</p> <p>Active science programs on NBS and NBS management</p>	<p>Building a community: Develop a communication strategy for NbS together with the largest landowners (e.g., Staatsbosbeheer) for local tourism</p> <p>Kitchen table talks with landowners and other stakeholders</p>
Kampinos wetland rewetting PL	<p>Primary goals: Biodiversity net gain, Climate regulation, Drought resilience, Flood resilience, Inclusivity, Health & well-being, Zero pollution</p> <p>Secondary goals: Financing the transition, Green growth, Sustainable food systems</p>	<p>Wetland rewetting mowing of grassland vegetation removal of invasive species</p> <p>Creation of new habitats</p> <p>Reintroduction of species construction of paths, shelters, playgrounds, educational boards, and other infrastructure for tourists and visitors</p> <p>Active nature conservation activities and related job creation</p>	<p>'Flowing Mazovia' Regional Scalability Plan as a main driver for an integrated approach to the management of the area</p> <p>Land purchase</p> <p>Promote and implement of agro-environmental programmes</p>	<p>Study of carbon and greenhouse gas balance in KNP, analysis of ecosystem services on their different services, including biodiversity and drought and flood resilience</p> <p>Assessment of the impact of the Regional Scalability Plan on ecosystem services</p>	<p>Analysis of protection needs against flooding among local communities continuous education of all stakeholders</p> <p>Training of Kampinos National Park staff in communication and problem-solving skills</p>
Hutovo Blato peatland rewetting BiH	Not received in time				

Case study	Green Deal goals	Measures in the field suggested to reach the goals	Policy domain actions (rules, regulations)	Research domain actions	Social domain actions
Danube floodplain restoration AT	<p>Primary goal: biodiversity net gain</p> <p>Secondary goals: climate, flood and drought resilience and inclusivity</p>	<p>Shoreline restoration through removal of bank protection</p> <p>Groyne optimization</p> <p>Secondary flow channels</p> <p>Side channel reconnection</p> <p>Fish passages</p> <p>Floodplain reconnection for flood and drought resilience</p> <p>Water retention for agriculture</p>	<p>River restoration strategy for the entire Austrian Danube, including all relevant stakeholders.</p>	<p>Monitoring impacts of restoration measures</p>	<p>Improving accessibility of freshwater ecosystems.</p> <p>Awareness raising.</p> <p>Early stakeholder involvement in restoration programmes.</p>
Danube sidearm reconnect HU	<p>Primary goals: climate regulation, biodiversity net gain, inclusivity.</p> <p>Secondary goals: sustainable transport, flood and drought resilience, health and wellbeing, sustainable food systems</p>	<p>Implement pilot floodplain restoration projects, mitigate shipping impacts, and promote sustainable forestry management and agriculture</p>	<p>Advocating at the governmental level for strategic large-scale restoration of the river-floodplain system</p> <p>Prioritise local-scale restoration actions</p>	<p>Develop and implement a monitoring program of NATURA 2000 habitats and species.</p> <p>Demonstrate the effectiveness of restoration actions to stakeholders and society</p> <p>Research and knowledge building needs to be part of stakeholder engagement</p>	<p>Facilitating intensified cooperation among stakeholders to formulate a sustainable landscape and water management plan for the region</p>
Danube floodplain reconnect RO	<p>Primary goals: flood and drought resilience, biodiversity net gain, climate regulation, inclusivity</p> <p>Secondary goals: health and well-being, sustainable food system, circular economy, financing the transition, and green growth</p>	<p>Implement restoration projects for floodplain water bodies and riparian forests</p> <p>Creation of flood retention areas using NbS</p> <p>Reconnect floodplains</p> <p>Water stewardship programs</p> <p>Zonation of accessibility</p> <p>Identify restoration supporting landowners</p>	<p>Cooperate with authorities to include wetland restoration in plans for flood risk management, river basin management and CAP</p> <p>Develop a policy to set catchment limits on water usage</p> <p>Identify resource requirements, including funding</p> <p>Create investment initiatives for green growth</p>	<p>Partner with scientific institutions to model the impact of climate scenarios.</p> <p>Monitoring to gain evidence on flood resilience in pilot sites</p>	<p>Outreach activities to raise awareness for NbS floodplain restoration</p> <p>Develop and implement ecotourism</p> <p>Offer assistance to farmers to develop sustainable agriculture jointly with wetlands restoration in pilot sites</p>

Case study	Green Deal goals	Measures in the field suggested to reach the goals	Policy domain actions (rules, regulations)	Research domain actions	Social domain actions
Tisza floodplain rewetting HU	<p>Primary goals: climate regulation, biodiversity net gain, drought resilience, sustainable food systems, inclusivity</p> <p>Secondary goals: flood resilience, health and wellbeing, financing the translation, circular economy, green growth</p>	<p>Pilot Natural water retention projects to restore the sponge function, reconnect floodplains and restore wetlands.</p> <p>Carbon sinking through extensive farming, wetland restoration and reforestation.</p> <p>Floodplain and organic farming</p> <p>Accessibility for tourism</p> <p>Water capture through retention and infiltration</p>	<p>Key stakeholder cooperation to develop the sustainable Tisza river basin strategy</p> <p>Lobby intensively to change the water management policy, land use policy and CAP subsidies framework in a positive direction</p> <p>Form an advocacy network for NWRM</p>	<p>Macroeconomic analysis of the benefits transition to NWRM in the Tisza Region</p>	<p>Public access to environmental information</p> <p>Public active involvement in the transformation of land use</p>
Blue Belt Germany DE	<p>Primary goals: biodiversity net gain, climate regulation, flood & drought resilience, health and well-being</p> <p>Secondary goals: zero pollution, green growth, sustainable transport, financing, and inclusive participation</p>	<p>Catalog of Blue Belt measures: removing bank protection, restoring floodplain water bodies, relocating dikes, restoring natural flow regimes and dynamics</p>	<p>The cooperation between the Federal Ministry for Digital and Transport (BMDV) and the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety, and Consumer Protection (BMUV) is essential to keep the long-term program running and to stimulate that new projects are initiated</p> <p>Interaction with the Blue Belt stakeholder board</p> <p>Mobilise additional funding</p>	<p>Habitat restoration and biodiversity: Assessing current state, threats, restoration potentials, and impacts on biodiversity.</p> <p>Ecosystem Dynamics: Studying species flows, pollutant transfer, and sediment balance.</p> <p>Ecosystem Services and NbS: Supporting restoration through ecosystem services and assessing Nature-based Solutions.</p> <p>Technology: Developing automated methods for monitoring and detecting habitats and invasive species</p>	<p>Integrate citizen science</p> <p>Engage local communities</p> <p>Environmental education</p> <p>Enlarge public access to restoration sites</p>

Case study	Green Deal goals	Measures in the field suggested to reach the goals	Policy domain actions (rules, regulations)	Research domain actions	Social domain actions
Emscher basin restoration DE	<p>Primary goals: biodiversity net gain, drought resilience and inclusivity</p> <p>Secondary goals: health and well-being, sustainable food systems, circular economy and green growth.</p>	<p>Flowering meadows for biodiversity, reinforce dike stability and attractive landscapes. Using the harvest for biogas production</p> <p>Participatory farming through cooperation with Allmende</p>	<p>Promotion of participatory agriculture in the form of self-sufficiency farming</p>	<p>Testing and developing charcoal processes</p>	<p>Citizen science as an inclusive, participatory citizen involvement.</p> <p>CrowdWater project to involve citizens.</p>
Lima floodplain forest restoration PT	<p>Primary goals: Biodiversity net gain, Drought resilience, Health & Human well-being, Inclusivity</p> <p>Secondary goals: Climate regulation, Zero pollution, Sustainable food system, Green Growth</p>	<p>Continuing and expanding the protection and restoration of key Natura 2000 habitats – improving the connectivity among habitat</p> <p>Develop integrated monitoring systems for a better understanding of the hydrology and biodiversity developments over time</p> <p>Increase walking routes through habitat areas subject to recovery/restoration</p>	<p>Purchase land in the protected area to maintain natural pastures for indigenous breeds</p> <p>Establish agreements or partnerships with landowners</p>	<p>Gain insight into the floodplain ecosystem trajectory after restoration, developing novel indicators of restoration success, reinforcing knowledge about plant-pollinator links along degradation gradients, reinforcement of the knowledge of the catchment and floodplain hydrology</p>	<p>Raising awareness and training farmers and other stakeholders</p> <p>Developing a Citizen Science initiative</p> <p>The involvement of stakeholders will be reinforced by replicating the MERLIN methodology</p>
Sorraia river restoration PT	<p>Primary goals: Biodiversity net gain, Sustainable Food Systems, Zero pollution, Climate-related, health and well-being, inclusivity</p> <p>Secondary goals: flood and drought resilience, sustainable transport, sustainable energy</p>	<p>Reforestation, vegetated buffers, ecological corridors, removal of invasive species, sustainable farming</p>	<p>Overcome policy barriers, particularly within CAP legislation, but these are considered to be outside the sphere of influence.</p>	<p>Writing guidelines for environmentally friendly river crossings after follow-up and validation using migratory fish species.</p> <p>Identify and study new NbS for riparian areas and rivers, notably pre-technological solutions</p>	<p>Education programs, Citizen science projects, community advisory boards, public access to green spaces, develop programs that integrate physical activity and nature exposure and knowledge building</p>

Case study	Green Deal goals	Measures in the field suggested to reach the goals	Policy domain actions (rules, regulations)	Research domain actions	Social domain actions
Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI	Primary goals; climate regulation, biodiversity net gain and inclusivity secondary goals: Sustainable energy	No direct measures but intended knowledge measures influence practices in the field	Seek funding to design an online planning tool that presents different options for the after-use of peat extraction sites Discuss with other actors how to continue with activities in the post 2030 period (after JTF finishes)	Plan and seek funding for a pilot project that assesses the synergies and trade-offs between potentially very profitable renewable energy systems (wind and solar) and biodiversity actions	Plan, implement and seek funding for a national-level restoration platform that connects landowners and those interested to fund exemplify different modes of collaboration for restoration
Tzipori basin restoration IL	<i>Primary goals:</i> Climate regulation, Biodiversity, Inclusivity <i>Secondary goals:</i> Floods and droughts resilience, Green growth Health and wellbeing, Zero pollution, Sustainable food systems	Reconnecting floodplains Physical recreation of wadi Improve recreational infrastructure Removal of weirs Reforestation of riverine corridor in three places Restoration of springs and wetlands Upgrading 2 WWTPs and sewer systems	Alteration of flow management and water abstraction regulations Develop and implement protocols for agro-ecological management with financial support Upgrade water allocation system for sustainable water use (including usage of desalinated water) Financial support for buffer strips along agricultural fields	Initiate practical research on agro-ecological issues in the catchment area in collaboration with researchers	Leadership development and engagement with the public through public participation Specific knowledge goals for both the team, professional stakeholders throughout Israel and local stakeholders Training of farmers for innovative cultivation and treatment methods
Upper Scheldt restoration BE	Primary goals: biodiversity net gain, climate regulation, inclusivity, zero pollution Secondary goals: flood and drought resilience, circular economy, sustainable energy, reduction in erosion, health and well-being	Execute plans and seek funding to make rivers more weather-extreme resilient Enlarge the sponge function of soils Grass-flower buffer strips to increase biodiversity and reduce erosion Improve free-flowing conditions and water quality River restoration to increase buffer capacity	Obtaining long-term sustainable funding is crucial. Make use of the funding opportunities that arose due to the recent problems with extreme events and climate change Having clear regulations and legislation	Knowledge-building of determining how much nutrients from the surface run-off is intercepted by the grass-flower strips through modeling and field monitoring	Involve water managers, farmers and other key stakeholders in decision-making on restoration actions Engage municipalities to support ecological restoration Communicate with the large public to get support for planned actions.

Case study	Green Deal goals	Measures in the field suggested to reach the goals	Policy domain actions (rules, regulations)	Research domain actions	Social domain actions
Forth basin restoration UK	<p>Primary goals: Biodiversity, Climate Regulation, Flood and Drought Resilience, Zero Pollution goals, Green Economy, Circular economy</p> <p>Secondary goals: Knowledge goals, Health and wellbeing, sustainable transport, energy and food systems</p>	<p>Removal of barriers for fish</p> <p>Morphological improvements of river</p> <p>Reforest riparian zones</p> <p>Implement and monitor various NFM measures (for flood) and water quality measures</p> <p>Increase agro-ecological farming</p> <p>Peatland restoration and lowland bog management</p>	<p>Clear administration of areas restored/to be restored is available for all</p> <p>Instigate a scheme for treating non-native invasives</p> <p>Create a standard for quantifying biodiversity net gain</p> <p>More flexible agri-environment schemes and payment processes for landowners to facilitate the sacrifice of land for biodiversity</p> <p>Write a catchment management plan for each river catchment with the steering group</p> <p>Scottish Invasive Species Initiative</p> <p>Facility for Investment Ready Nature</p>		<p>Work with stakeholders in implementing measures</p> <p>Give feedback on results of restoration actions to those involved</p> <p>Citizen science and Community Involvement actions</p> <p>Provide training for farmers and landowners on sustainable management of their lands</p> <p>Encourage local authorities to invest in NbS as opposed to grey solutions</p> <p>Create steering groups for each catchment group</p>

All RSPs include multiple Green Deal goals. Biodiversity net gain is a primary goal in all RSPs and for the great majority also climate regulation³ and inclusivity (Table 4). Flood and drought resilience, health and wellbeing are either a primary or secondary goal for most case studies. Other goals are mostly secondary or considered not relevant for the case study.

Table 4 Overview of primary (1; blue) and secondary goals (2; green) per case study

#	Name	Biodiversity Net gain	Climate regulation	Inclusivity	Drought resilience	Flood resilience	Health & Wellbeing	Zero-pollution	Farm to Fork	Circular economy	Green growth	Financing the transition	Sustainable Energy	Sustainable transport	Primary	Secondary
Peatlands & wetlands																
1	Kvorning	1	1	1		2	2	1							4	2
3	Beaver re-introduction	1	2	2	2	2		2	2				2		1	7
5	Kampinos	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2		2	2			7	3
6	Hutovo Blato														0	0
12	Lima	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	2		2				5	4
14	Kompassuo	1	1	1									2		3	1
17	Forth	1	1		1	1	2	1	2	1	1			2	7	3
Small stream & basins																
2	Deba	1	1	1		1	2	2			2				4	3
11	Emscher	1	1	1	1		2		2	2	2	2	2		4	6
13	Sorraia	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1		2		2	2	6	5
15	Tzipori	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2		2				3	6
16	Upper Scheldt	1	1	1	2	2	2	1		2			2		4	5
Large transboundary rivers																
4	Room for the Rhine	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	2			2		2	4	6
7a	Danube Austria	1	2	2	2	2									1	4
7b	Danube Hungary	1	1	1	2	2	2		2					2	3	5
8	Danube Romania	1	1	1	1	1	2		2	2	2	2			5	5
9	Tisza	1	1	1	1	2	2		1	2	2	2			5	5
10	Blue Belt	1	1	2	1	1	1	2			2	2		2	5	5
Primary		17	14	13	7	6	5	5	2	1	1	0	0	0		
Secondary		0	3	3	7	9	9	6	9	4	9	6	5	5		

3.7 Stakeholders of RSP (WHO)

In the MERLIN project, the stakeholder engagement builds on the previous experience and contacts of the case studies as well as on the stakeholder boards created as advisory boards for MERLIN restoration projects. Typically, government agencies with relevant policy expertise and jurisdiction over the case study area (e.g., water basin), as well as nature conservation and research actors, were invited to the stakeholder boards. Upscaling restoration and the development of RSP required also extending and expanding stakeholder engagement to cover new topical areas (e.g., inclusion of forestry requires forestry actors) and new jurisdictional areas (e.g., regional government). The RSP development and tools, such as the self-assessment on upscaling (2.2), fostered holistic planning. When working with the stakeholders to develop the RSP, both the Green Deal goals and Nature-based Solutions- concept helped to identify common issues as well as underline

³ It is possible there is confusion regarding whether it is climate regulation or rather mitigation and adaptation. This is an aspect we, the authors of the synthesis did not properly check with the individual case studies.

differences. In some cases, other integrative concepts such as “habitat network” helped to build stakeholder interaction and expand networks (Blue Belt Germany DE).

In the RSP development, collaboration with national, regional, and local government actors, such as ministries, regulatory agencies and municipalities, has been vital. Typically, the government stakeholders represent the areas of agriculture, climate, disaster management, environmental protection, forestry, navigation, spatial planning and water management. In some RSPs, policymakers include also local politicians in key positions of power, such as mayors. The government actors are important and powerful stakeholders due to their diverse roles in restoration policies, such as agenda setters, policy designers, regulators, implementers, and funders. Public actors, such as national park authorities and municipalities, can also be important landowners, and landowners are crucial stakeholders in deciding whether and what kind of restoration measures are possible. Furthermore, in some RSPs, the jurisdictional boundaries of a government entity also influenced the upscaling area (i.e., WHERE) and the upscaling area was defined using these boundaries (e.g., Upper Scheldt restoration BE, Lima floodplain forest restoration PT).

In addition to the government and public sector, the private sector is a key change agent. In terms of private sector, the MERLIN project has sought linkages with six economic sectors considered to be crucial for transformative change in freshwater restoration: agriculture, hydropower, insurance, navigation, peat extraction, and water supply and sanitation (Table 5). The inclusion of the agricultural sector, particularly farmers, has been successful, but there have been challenges in terms of hydropower and insurance sectors. Peat extraction was a key stakeholder in two peatland cases, while in other peatland cases, agriculture was a more dominant economic sector. Additionally, other extractive land uses, forestry and fisheries, emerged as a key economic sector and landowner in 7 RSPs, including 3 peatland cases. In the Room for the Rhine NL RSP, the clay and sand industry that extracts river basin materials was a potential funder of restoration activities. Navigation represented a key stakeholder for the RSPs addressing large rivers, but not for peatlands and small streams and basins. Furthermore, in relation to navigation, public sector actors dominated, highlighting the need to explore the possibilities of bringing in private navigation actors.

In addition to the 6 economic sectors identified in MERLIN, we also examined whether tourism was featured in the RSPs. Freshwater restoration was linked with improved (eco)tourism possibilities in many RSPs, but only 4 RSPs specifically referred to tourism actors. However, tourism may be represented by other stakeholders, such as local development associations or farmers engaging in agritourism.

The involvement of civil society (e.g., NGOs) is important to include diverse interests and voices in the RSPs. In terms of civil society, particularly environmental conservation and protection, NGOs are well presented across the RSPs. It is important to also highlight that some of the MERLIN case studies (including case study implementation and the RSP development) have been initiated by civil society actors, such as Danube sidearm reconnect HU (7b), Tisza floodplain rewetting HU (9) and Danube floodplain reconnect RO (8). This emphasizes that civil society actors have a pivotal role in pushing for more ambitious environmental and climate policies. In addition to environmental NGOs, a wide range of other NGOs and associations are included. These civil society actors work from local to national level and present the perspectives of local resource users and recreation interests (e.g., local fishers, kayakers) as well as cultural and local heritage.

The larger public is presented through local communities in the form of community and village groups. We also considered projects targeting locals through citizen science as a form of local community engagement. In some RSPs, community groups are not explicitly named if the RSPs are focused on very populated areas or consisting of many sub-projects (Forth basin restoration UK and Kvorning wetland rewetting DK). For example, the Forth basin restoration RSP will consult local communities project-by-project or by sub-river catchment before any work planning is started (UK Forth case study personal communication 10.6.2024).

Furthermore, the research community is an important stakeholder who provides knowledge and assesses the effectiveness of measures. The RSPs highlight the need for more knowledge in terms of identifying potential restoration sites, interested landowners, financial measures as well as restoration outcomes. The effectiveness of measures is crucial to understanding and promoting the best restoration and Nature-based Solutions for topics such as flood control. Given that Nature-based Solutions often compete with grey solutions (e.g., natural flood management techniques vs. building dams and walls), acquiring long-term monitoring data is crucial and was highlighted by multiple RSPs. Research and science-based information also form the backbone of collaborations and cooperation across sectors, a key issue for many RSPs.

Table 5 Presence of sectors and other key groups in MERLIN case study RSPs. For the number and names of the RSPs and related case studies see Annex 7.1.

	Peatlands		Small streams		Large rivers	
	Public	Private	Public	Private	Public	Private
Agriculture (including farmers and farmers' associations)	1, 5, 12,17	1, 5, 17	2, 13	2, 13, 15, 16	4,7a, 7b, 8, 9	4,8,9,10
Hydropower	12			2	7a	
Insurance						
Navigation					4, 7a, 7b 8, 10	4
Peat extraction	17, 14	14				
Water Supply and Sanitation	3, 5, 17		13	16	4, 7b	4
OTHER key groups						
Nature conservation (NGOs)	1, 5, 12, 14, 17		2, 11, 13, 16		7a, 7b, 8, 9, 10	
Commercial forest and fisheries sectors	3, 12, 14		13		7b, 8, 9	
Local communities (e.g. village groups, area-focused citizen science initiatives)	5, 12, 14, 17		2, 13, 16		10	
NGOs and associations (e.g. local fishing and hunting associations, local development association, recreation NGOs)	1, 3, 5, 12, 14, 17		13		7a, 7b, 9, 10	
Tourism sector (tourism association, tourism companies)			15		7a, 9, 10	

3.7.1 Types of stakeholder engagement

In addition to types of stakeholders, also types of engagement in the RSPs were examined. Stakeholder engagement can have multiple different and diverse goals. Identifying the right stakeholders and choosing the appropriate types of stakeholder engagement is important yet challenging. Building on the idea of ladder of participation (i.e., information, consultation, collaboration, cooperation and empowerment) by Arnstein (1969) and Grygoruk and Rannow (2017) (Figure 6), we look at how different intensities of stakeholder engagement manifest in the RSPs. In the MERLIN project and the RSPs, stakeholder engagement has ranged from being informed to collaboration and cooperation. Empowerment is not featured in the analysis, as we interpreted that the RSP should be adopted by stakeholders, for the empowerment-criteria to be filled. For now, many of the RSPs are still finding their way into policy and practice and are not actively taken forwards by all the stakeholders.

Figure 6 Different intensities of stakeholder engagement, taken from Grygoruk and Rannow (2017)

Compared to the draft-RSP plans (Pietilä et al. 2023), the stakeholder engagement has found new target audiences and goals. Some of these forms are hard to fit into a single category, such as advocacy (e.g., 1, 13), capacity building (e.g., 5, 8, 9, 17) and personal meetings and discussions (e.g., 1, 10, 16). Advocacy can entail that stakeholders promote the restoration goals and encourage their networks to join restoration projects (e.g., 1, 5) or that stakeholders provide funding that enables the organization of local events (13). Similarly, RSPs highlight the role of strengthening collaborative networks and institutional partnerships (e.g., 7b, 8, 9, 13, 14), which entail diverse intensities of engagement (i.e., information provision, consultation, collaboration and cooperation). Personal communication plays a significant role in cases of mistrust and resistance or sensitive topics such as ownership issues.

The RSPs contain much information about stakeholders, planned interactions and intended goals. The RSP of Blue Belt Germany DE (10) also includes a short section on the engagement insights gained through ongoing and completed restoration projects (16 projects). These insights will feed to inform the stakeholder engagement in future (30 planned) projects. Furthermore, the development of the RSP document itself has played a role in boosting and fostering collaboration and cooperation. For example, in the case of Kampinos wetland rewetting-PL, the RSP was listed as a work item by the Coordination Council of the UNESCO Biosphere Reserve “Puszcza Kampinowska.

Below are highlighted examples of different types of stakeholder engagement, categorized by intensity. The engagement may be done by the case study coordinators or by a stakeholder. Depending on the goal, an engagement tool can be categorized in different ways. For example, developing educational programs provides environmental information for students, however, building educational programs in collaboration with other stakeholders strengthens interactions and builds capacity. It is also good to acknowledge that RSPs link to multiple strategies, where stakeholders in fact control the process and final decision making. However, this is the result of social and political order. Furthermore, given the conceptual ambiguity of empowerment, it can also be interpreted in the context of e.g., personal life. In this regard, action, such as participation in environmental citizen science, can help people to gain agency and feel empowered.

Information

- Local websites, newspapers, social media, films and citizen science are used to communicate about ecosystem restoration and biodiversity conservation (ALL), organizing workshops, trainings and events regarding specific topics (4,5, 10,12)
- Developing educational programs for children, young people and wider communities to enhance environmental stewardship (7b, 10, 11, 12, 13) and advisory services for farmers related to environmentally friendly farming practices and climate change impacts (8, 9, 17)
- Access to restoration site is improved by creating trails and providing educational signages (10, 12, 13, 14, 15), organization of guided tours and field trips (10, 11, 13), showcase measures

Consultation

- Interviews, surveys and personal discussions with stakeholders help to understand their needs, concerns and preferences (1, 5, 7a, 7b, 12), for example, regarding land use
- Public consultations will be organized regarding restoration (9)

Collaboration

- Stakeholders' knowledge and perspectives can be used to modify restoration projects in terms of size, location and restoration action so that they better align with stakeholder concerns and ecological needs (ALL). Further, stakeholders help to identify priority areas (8, 10), relevant Green Deal goals (4, 7a), understand local needs (5, 2)
- Local communities and experts interact in workshops that discuss water resource management strategies (5)
- Citizen science forms an essential part of (future) data collection and restoration project stakeholder engagement activities (10, 11, 13, 16)
- RSP will strengthen collaboration with different actors such as local agencies, farmers and researchers and build networks working on restoration and Nature-based Solutions (3, 7b, 8, 9, 13, 14) as well as topics such as sustainable food systems (12) and water management (7b)

Cooperation

- Stakeholder boards of MERLIN case study participate in RSP development (ALL)
- RSP helps to strengthen cooperation of a multi-stakeholder platform (5)
- Development of new local economy models with land users (9, 17)
- Community advisory boards will be established to enable participation in decision-making processes related to land use and conservation (9, 13)
- Working with local champions who are living “best practices” of restoration (12)

3.8 Who is missing in the RSPs?

In addition to looking at who is engaged, we also examine the sectors that are missing in the RSPs.

Financial and environmental service market

The absence of insurance, banking and environmental service markets is noteworthy. Despite the rise in market-based approaches to conservation, such as carbon and biodiversity credit and offsets, as well as green bonds, these approaches are still marginal (Demsey & Suarez 2016). During the MERLIN project, innovative financial instruments or so-called off-the-shelf instruments have been reviewed in WP3. Current reviews cover the options and possibilities provided by three instruments (i.e., donation-based crowdfunding and tourism and agriculture activities) and will still cover others, including carbon sequestration credits, mutual guarantees, grants, biodiversity offsetting, public-private partnerships, debt instruments, and climate bonds. These reviews will be available through the MERLIN website.

(Private) landowners interested in restoration

Many of the RSPs highlight the challenges related to identifying landowners who are interested in restoration. Landowners are a highly diverse group, as they may be individuals, estates, private companies, public companies and municipalities and national parks. Some RSPs are working with large landowners (e.g., Forth basin restoration UK, Sorraia River restoration PT) who may become thus restoration “champions” and play a key role in demonstrating new nature-friendly practices and sharing their experiences to other landowners. In many countries, however, land is owned by small landowners with land parcels at different locations. RSPs work with farmers' associations to reach out to the smaller landowners, and thus, associations can play a key role in this regard. Furthermore, several RSPs note that upscaling restoration will require (or is likely to require) land buy-back and land swap programs (e.g., Kvorning wetland rewetting DK, Kampinos wetland rewetting PL, Room for the Rhine NL, Emscher basin restoration DE, Upper Scheldt restoration BE).

National freshwater restoration networks

In the small river cluster, networks, networks-of-networks as well as communities of practice were featured in the RSPs in diverse roles. However, in the peatland-wetlands and large river clusters, networks were less prominent (except for the Kvorning wetland rewetted DK, the Danube floodplain restoration AT and the Tisza floodplain rewetted HU). Several RSPs in these clusters explicitly mention the need to establish networks and communities of practice to effectively communicate and spread best practices (Beaver river engineering SE, Room for the Rhine NL, Komppasuo peatland rewetted FI). Furthermore, the need to strengthen cross-sectoral collaboration as well as engage different types of stakeholders suggests that there is a need for national networks.

Education and Communication sector

Many RSPs feature awareness-raising, training and educational activities for diverse audiences (e.g., school children, government staff, farmers), but the actors representing these sectors are not strongly present in the RSPs. For example, in terms of farmers, the LEADER programs and agricultural extension services would be an important partner. However, these kinds of advisory services may be reached by working with farmers' associations. Overall, the need for stakeholder engagement and interaction is widely emphasized, but only a few RSPs take a more strategic approach and explicitly mention the need to create a communication strategy for their activities (e.g., Room for the Rhine NL, Tisza floodplain rewetted HU, Sorraia river restoration PT). To ensure effective engagement and communication with stakeholders, there is a need to bring experts from the education and communication sector.

4 Summary of scaling out, scaling up, and scaling deep per cluster

This chapter specifically focuses on the different concepts of scaling up from individual pilot cases to overarching regional strategies. It distinguishes three different aspects of scaling that are needed to reach overarching goals: scaling out, scaling up and scaling deep (see chapter 1.4). The idea is to shed light on the different kinds of activities needed in impactful upscaling by showcasing examples from the RSPs.

Scaling out identifies measures and strategies that will be continued and carried out in the larger RSP area. In addition to ecological restoration measures (e.g., rewetting), also stakeholder interaction strategies can be scaled out. Scaling up identifies measures targeting policy and practice change. Scaling deep is about the measures that address values, attitudes and behavior. Since value and attitude change underpins policy and practice change, the categories of scaling up and scaling deep are often overlapping and mutually supportive. Furthermore, some measures such as “training and communication” are truly crosscutting, as these could be classified as scaling out (i.e., repeated actions), scaling up (i.e., aiming for policy change) or scaling up (aiming for attitude and behavior change). In the following Tables 6-8, we have categorized these information-based activities with clear link to policy under “scaling up” and otherwise, these were categorized under “scaling deep”. If there was a clear desire to repeat the communication/ stakeholder engagement, it was classified as “scaling out”. The results are presented in clusters: peatlands and wetlands, small streams and basins and large rivers.

4.1 Peatlands and wetlands cluster

In the peatlands and wetlands, **scaling out** focusses on the introduction and continuation of restoration measures such as rewetting, reforestation, invasive species control, natural flood control measures and re-introduction of beavers. In the Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI and Lima floodplain forest restoration PT, scaling out also relates to replicating best practices in land use planning (i.e., “socially wise land use”) and societal engagement with landowners. In the case of the Kampinos wetland rewetting PL, an essential aspect of scaling out is that the restoration actions support ecological corridors between the national park and surrounding areas.

Scaling up entails changes in practices and policies in areas such as farming and agriculture, forestry, and water resource and risk management. Also, improving multi-stakeholder collaborations and building networks are needed to help spread new ideas (e.g., beaver management) and support restoration. Value change (**scaling out**) is mostly approached through awareness raising, voluntary participation in land consolidation schemes, provision of easy-to-access knowledge and trainings. However, by improving multi-stakeholder collaboration, there is a possibility for enhanced understanding between different actors. This emphasizes the close connections between scaling up (changing policies and practices) and scaling deep (value and behavioral change). The Forth basin restoration UK RSP also highlights the role of narratives, i.e., how actors are depicted and suggests that land managers, for example, could be depicted as conservation agents who actively take up restoration on their lands.

Table 6 Examples of scaling activities in RSPs in the peatlands and wetlands cluster

Case study	Scaling out (replication) = what is replicated?	Scaling up (policy change) = How are policies or practices changed or supported?	Scaling deep (value change) = how are underlying values and attitudes changed?
Kvorning wetland rewetting DK	Rewetting of carbon-rich soils (peat soil) on 100.000 ha. of currently farmed/drained land, and adjacent areas	<p>Network of project managers throughout the Danish Nature Agency nationally, supported by the Headquarters</p> <p>National corps of agricultural consultants, financed by the government, advising the farmers on topics related to taking carbon-rich soils/farmland out of production</p> <p>National task force and national expert group giving recommendations to the policymakers regarding obstacles for reaching the goal of taking 100.000 (140.000) hectares out of production by 2023</p>	<p>Common meetings. Personal, in-depth meetings with individual landowners</p> <p>Corps of agricultural consultants, advising farmers on topics related to engaging in a re-wetting project</p>
Beaver river engineering SE	Beaver re-introduction so that positive effects are maximized and negative effects are minimized	Building a national beaver network that can promote best practice	Awareness raising and provision of easy-to-access knowledge on beavers
Kampinos wetland rewetting PL	<p>Measures and projects restoring wetlands and enhancing biodiversity as well as supporting ecological corridors with surrounding areas.</p> <p>Measures to improve water resource and water risk management</p>	<p>Establishment of a working group on public expectations with the coordinating council of the RSP</p> <p>Capacity building of national park and municipality staff</p>	<p>Education, awareness raising and communication training</p> <p>Multi-stakeholder collaboration that includes local communities</p>
Hutovo Blato peatland rewetting BiH	Not received on time		
Lima floodplain forest restoration PT	Forest restoration and controlling invasive species, societal engagement with landowners	<p>Forest management to support planting and use of native forest species (rather than exotic species)</p> <p>Use of alternative approaches to promote wetland habitat recovery (such as passive restoration)</p>	<p>Raising awareness and training key stakeholders (e.g., farmers) about the importance of balanced ecosystems</p> <p>Educational programs for children</p> <p>Evidence-informed policymaking and adaptive management in restoration</p>
Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI	Socially wise land use in former peat extraction sites so that climate, biodiversity and water impacts are considered	Creating a multi-stakeholder platform to strengthen collaboration among diverse actors working on peatland restoration	Awareness raising and provision of easy-to-access knowledge on best practices

Case study	Scaling out (replication) = what is replicated?	Scaling up (policy change) = How are policies or practices changed or supported?	Scaling deep (value change) = how are underlying values and attitudes changed?
Forth basin restoration UK	Biodiversity enhancement through peatland rewetting and natural flood management measures	Co-production of policies (e.g., regional initiative for invasive species) Training and upskilling for diverse stakeholders Development of new finance models	Building communication links and understanding between sectors (energy, transport, environmental NGOs and Nature Scot) to reduce conflict Capacity building Explicit narrative change, e.g., in considering land managers as conservation agents

4.2 Small streams and basins cluster

Scaling out focused on river restoration measures such as implementing grass-flower buffer strips and barrier and obstacle (e.g., dam) removal to enable free-flowing river and tree planting. The Tzipori basin restoration IL implemented a very inclusive stakeholder engagement in their pilot project and the RSP would seek to use a similar process. Similar to the peatlands and wetlands cluster, **scaling up** entailed strengthening networks, particularly those at the municipal level. In terms of **scaling deep**, building communication channels, raising awareness, and conducting personal discussions were highlighted. Also, environmental education initiatives and citizen science were featured in several RSPs. The use of local champions (e.g. Sorraia river restoration PT) can be considered as an example that scales up (changes practices) but also scales deep (value change through peer-to-peer learning).

Table 7 Examples of scaling activities in RSPs in the small streams and basins cluster.

Case study	Scaling out (replication) = what is replicated?	Scaling up (policy change) = how are policies or practices changed or supported?	Scaling deep (value change) = how are underlying values and attitudes changed?
Deba barrier removal ES	Monitoring schemes, obstacle (e.g., dam) removal from rivers	Establishing local mayors' platform to discuss restoration progress and problems	Evidence-informed communication to public showcasing results and building channels that enable dialogue between citizens and research projects
Emscher basin restoration DE	Establishment of flowering meadows	Pilots to overcome bottlenecks related to biodiversity-enhancing grassland management	Using citizen science to empower people to act
Sorraia river restoration PT	River rehabilitation measures such as indigenous tree planting and erosion control using natural materials	Promoting local champions and setting best practices to facilitate restoration action among neighbors Building institutional partnerships, e.g., collaborations between different stakeholders	Promoting local champions and setting best practices to facilitate restoration action among neighbors Awareness raising on river restoration and providing training on the management of riparian areas for farmers Development of educational programs, e.g., environmental education for local schools
Tzipori basin restoration IL	River restoration Inclusive stakeholder community engagement	RSP is a structured framework for stakeholders for efficient, effective and legitimate restoration Building cross-sectoral collaboration	Building collaboration across diverse (ethnic) groups Education programs
Upper Scheldt restoration BE	River habitat restoration measures with focus on free fish migration and implementation of buffer strips to enhance biodiversity and improve water quality	Strengthen synergies with existing initiatives such as Landscape park Vlaamse Ardennen Building engagement with different municipalities to support ecological restoration	Personal, in-depth discussions with farmers, supported by financial incentives to implement grass-flower buffer strips

4.3 Large rivers cluster

The RSPs of the large river cluster typically consist of large areas and thus, the scaling out measures are very diverse. In addition to promoting free-flowing rivers also reconnection of side arms and rewetting of floodplains are important measures. In terms of **scaling out**, mitigation of the negative impacts of river infrastructure is a key theme. This entails measures such as fish passages and infrastructure that allows inflow of water into previously closed floodplains. The Danube floodplain reconnect RO has been building multi-stakeholder collaborations and this work will be continued in the future when restoration efforts move to new areas.

Within the Large River cluster, **scaling up** entailed aligning RSP and the Nature-based Solutions into national and regional strategies and plans. The Blue Belt DE RSP is showcasing an existing government program with alignment with governmental strategies while the Tisza floodplain rewetting HU RSP aims to create a new, comprehensive strategy for the Tisza region. In addition to embedding the RSP into governmental policies, also enhanced collaboration and capacity building are important for policy change.

In terms of **scaling deep**, awareness raising, training and education are considered key. Enhancing cross-sectoral collaboration can help overcome siloes, but also monitoring data and evidence on the effectiveness and impacts of measures is needed when collaborating with stakeholders.

Two RSPs particularly are worth highlighting in this cluster as these RSPs build on long-term restoration initiatives. These initiatives and the MERLIN work have demonstrated that removing heavy engineering such as bank protection from rivers gives room for Nature-based Solutions while keeping the river suitable for navigation.

The first, the Room for the Rhine NL RSP builds on the Room for the River (1993 – 2018) program which was initiated after heavy flooding in 1993-1995⁴. The work conducted under this program can be considered a transformation from the traditional way of flood protection. It included different upscaling aspects. It scaled out through a wider set of measures, scaled up by combining flood risk reduction targets with environmental quality and scaling deep by its participatory approach with kitchen table meetings with local stakeholders and inhabitants.

The second RSP, Danube floodplain restoration AT, is an example of how an incremental approach rather than a transformative approach helps to take restoration forward. The restoration started in the 1990s with small-scale, risk-avoiding pilot projects. These pilots have developed into innovative, experimental and more risky projects, implemented jointly by viadonau and Donau Auen National park. This work underlines that scaling deep is underpinned by gradual changes in behavior through learning by doing, collecting evidence and increasing mutual appreciation (trust).

4

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/signals-archived/signals-2018-content-list/articles/interview-2014-the-dutch-make>

Table 8 Examples of scaling activities in RSPs in the large transboundary rivers cluster

Case study	Scaling out (replication) = what is replicated?	Scaling up (policy change) = how are policies or practices changed or supported?	Scaling deep (value change) = how are underlying values and attitudes changed?
Room for the Rhine NL	Implementing floodplain rewetting	Embedding Nature-based Solutions into existing long-term programmes	Education: organizing school activities, integrated training for civil servants and junior consultants
Danube floodplain restoration AT	Diverse river restoration e.g., removal of obstacles, such as hard riverbank structures, reconnecting side-arms, reducing riverbed incision, fish passage facilities	to integrate RSP into national strategies and management activities	education and awareness raising, e.g., what a natural river looks like, activities with schools
Danube sidearm reconnect HU	Wetland restoration and awareness-raising activities	Enhance cooperation with relevant authorities and stakeholders to include wetland restoration in relevant policies, e.g., Flood risk management and climate adaptation plans	enhancing cooperation with stakeholders to overcome siloes awareness raising and education Demonstrating restoration effectiveness through comprehensive monitoring
Danube floodplain reconnect RO	Restoration of human-modified landscapes (e.g., agricultural fields) Building multi-stakeholder collaborations with government authorities and other stakeholders	Capacity building of policy actors to develop more sustainable policies Enhancing multistakeholder collaboration	Cross-sectoral cooperation brings diverse perspectives and supports holistic problem-solving Awareness raising Research to examine underlying values and attitudes
Tisza floodplain rewetting HU	Sustainable land use and water efficiency in the floodplain lands	Creating a comprehensive government programme- Tisza Strategy- for the region with key stakeholders Policy lobbying to integrate new, water-based payment proposals	Inclusion and agency for stakeholders through communication, collaborative forums and case study boards of restoration projects
Blue Belt Germany DE	Restoration projects that build on the experience of previous Blue Belt projects, e.g., by using the “Catalogue of Blue Belt Measures”	Change is achieved as Blue Belt is an ongoing government program and aligns with government strategies, e.g., National Biodiversity and Tourism Strategy	Building shared understanding of integrated river landscapes through environmental education, multi-level participation and public outreach.

5 Recommendations and lessons learnt

The creation of the 16 Regional Scalability Plans has been a large endeavor within the MERLIN project. It started with the optimization of existing restoration projects (Buijse et al. 2022) and was followed by the development of interim Regional Scalability Plans (Pietilä et al. 2023) and a series of workshops with stakeholders to reach the final RSPs. In this chapter, we provide our recommendations and lessons learned based on the reflections of the authors of this report. Our recommendations cover both the process of creating the RSPs and the resulting products in the wider frame of upscaling freshwater ecosystem restoration throughout Europe.

5.1 Recommendations related to the RSP development process

Lesson 1. RSPs look different depending on their starting point.

As noted in Section 2.2, the starting point for the plans was very different and this influenced the level of maturity and concreteness that the final RSPs achieved. The Danish Kvorning wetland rewetting case, for example, was already very far along in terms of upscaling and thus is particularly useful as inspiration elsewhere in Europe. Others, however, such as Finland's Komppasuo peatland rewetting, was a completely new restoration project and thus the process of upscaling is in the initial stages.

Lesson 2. Upscaling requires a thorough understanding of local contexts, learning-by-doing and being adaptive.

Scaling can be considered as a multi-dimensional approach that includes different kinds of scaling activities towards “out” (i.e., replication), “up” (changing policies and practices) and “deep” (change in values and attitudes). “Scaling up” and “scaling deep” are partly overlapping concepts, as policy change may be underpinned by changes in values and attitudes and vice versa. In terms of scaling out, the MERLIN case studies have applied a diversity of measures in their restoration projects serving a wider set of goals. While these measures can be replicated elsewhere, it is essential that measure selection and design is guided by the local socio-ecological context. So, while measures are replicable, tailoring them need to consider the local context, i.e., the ecosystem characteristics, governance and policy as well as social actors. Learning-by-doing and adaptability as well as a robust, evidence-based understanding of the context, are thus key in scaling out.

Considering climate change and the increase in extreme weather events, there is quite likely a need to adapt measures to meet future climate conditions. Thus, assessing measure effectiveness through monitoring and research and adaptive management should be essential components of “scaling up”. Adaptation is underpinned by learning and requires flexibility, meaning that data about different systems (i.e., system monitoring) is crucial. Stakeholder awareness and understanding are important parts of adaptive management so that essential changes to plans can be carried out. Since, for many of the current RSPs, it is a starting point, adaptive management is not adequately recognized and addressed. It suffices to indicate that RSPs need to be revisited and adapted over time. Admittedly, ensuring system-level adaptation is very challenging, but the first step is very clear: ensuring that different systems are monitored properly to support the decision-making.

Lesson 3. Developing landscape level strategies as with RSPs requires sufficient time and resources to ensure rigorous planning and good stakeholder engagement.

Developing landscape-level strategies requires long processes that enable the identification of stakeholders, building trust and finding effective ways of working. The first drafts of RSPs were prepared by the MERLIN case study partners with limited interaction with stakeholders and limited internal feedback from the MERLIN project group (steering group). However, these aspects were addressed in the trajectory from draft plans to final RSP. This encompassed several workshops and meetings with actors at national, regional or local level. In addition to government and public bodies, also companies, farmers, non-governmental organisations, and local community associations were involved in this process. Running these kinds of processes requires both human and financial resources. Funding from the MERLIN project was essential in kick-starting the initiatives and elaborating the plans. Furthermore, giving the RSP development an adequate timeframe (2021-2024), synergies with other MERLIN work could be ensured.

Lesson 4. To avoid stakeholder fatigue, RSP events should preferably be scheduled jointly with other related topics. Ensuring an ambiance of trust and comfort is crucial, engaging with stakeholders “in their own environment”, such as homes or pubs, is sometimes key to good communication.

During the MERLIN project, the case studies closely interacted with the stakeholders relevant to their case. In most meetings and workshops, various aspects of the MERLIN project were discussed. This way the meeting could be used to both inform people about the project and to jointly discuss and co-develop ideas for further improvements both for the MERLIN restoration actions (Gerner et al. 2023) as well as the RSP development. Engaging stakeholders enabled to identify common issues of concern and to talk about their desires and needs. Some case studies also realized that discussing with locals in their environments, such as having talks at homes or local pubs, helped to create an ambiance of trust. However, in some instances, the process was hampered by single individuals with an opposing viewpoint taking a hard stand against the proposed initiatives. As the organizers of these meetings were often coming from the more biophysical/technical domains it was not always easy for them to deal with these opposing views, nor did they have the training or tools to help overcome stakeholder resistance. The ability to address and settle conflicts was also a topic of discussion during MERLIN project meetings (e.g., cluster meetings) and case studies exchanged views and experiences on this. In some RSPs (e.g., Kampinos rewetting PL), conflict resolution is part of the RSP activities. The staff of the national park responsible for planning and implementing the restoration measures got additional training in facilitating stakeholder processes and dialogues.

Lesson 5. Next to working with the stakeholders, freshwater restoration will benefit from more multidisciplinary teams, particularly to attract private funding.

Upscaling restoration, such as developing RSPs, requires multi-disciplinary teams where members represent researchers, practitioners and policymakers. People with a governance and social science background help understand how policies can be changed and how to work with stakeholders effectively. Experts in knowledge co-production and communication are vital to ensure that the processes are science-based and meaningful to stakeholders. However, the role of technical experts should be underestimated as their expertise helps to pay attention to the complex interlinkages between climate, environment and water, e.g., the role of wetland restoration for mitigating floods and droughts and carbon capture.

Similarly, economic and financial expertise is essential in budgeting, reaching out to potential funders, developing business models and identifying business opportunities. The current reliance on public funding in the RSPs highlights that restoration produces public goods (to be funded by the public sector). However, it also suggests that the teams developing RSPs are used almost solely to work with public money (including government representatives themselves). This means that private funding instruments and resources are still unfamiliar and under-explored territory for many.

Lesson 6. Despite political and economic turmoil, it is possible to advance ambitious restoration plans. From the restoration proponents, it requires perseverance and agility but also collective action.

The period in which the RSPs were developed (2021-2024) coincided with several local, regional and national elections, the COVID pandemic and the war in Ukraine. Elections shifted the political priorities and agendas of governments, which affected the development of RSPs (e.g., Belgium), especially in terms of what was feasible to achieve in the short term. Furthermore, the controversy and opposition related to the EU Nature Restoration Law (NRL) in 2023 and 2024 was especially challenging. If adopted, the law would provide great support to RSPs, particularly as countries would have to create national restoration plans and allocate the necessary budgets. The MERLIN RSPs were finalized in May 2024, so just before the final voting on NRL, which was then approved by a narrow majority. Thus, the RSPs had to ground their plans to other legal and funding instruments while acknowledging the opportunities that NRL potentially could bring.

Writing RSP teams had to look for alternative options, influence visions of desired futures, and influence the speed and direction of plans. This period also saw pressure from farmer protests against EU Green Deal ambitions all over Europe, including the Netherlands, Germany and Belgium, which highlighted the negative impacts of these ambitions. The COVID pandemic and war in Ukraine also influenced the debate on Green Deals ambitions, agriculture and energy production. External circumstances will change in the future and influence short-term priorities. Achieving the long-term ambitions of the RSPs requires perseverance and agility. This entails the repetition of the “old” messages that highlight the importance of restoration but also the ability to reach out to new audiences with new messages. Importantly, restoration needs legitimacy, and this can be achieved by building networks and collaborations.

5.2 Recommendations related to RSP content

Lesson 7. Using holistic and ambitious policy frameworks (e.g., the EU Green Deal, SMART) help support goal-setting in RSPs. Additionally, it helped to talk with government stakeholders.

The Green Deal goals framework served as a guideline for the MERLIN project proposal and for the work conducted under MERLIN. The RSPs and the Green Deal goals are connected in various ways. The RSP framework called for specificity in the goals and detailed actions. During the RSP development, the case studies were requested to apply the SMART criteria to goals and actions. The SMART criteria enhance effective planning that aims for goals and actions that are Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound.

In addition to SMART-planning, multiple RSPs also discuss how the work therein links to the Green Deal goals more broadly. Some RSPs only feature those goals that they make specific contributions to, e.g., Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI, while in others, e.g., Room for the Rhine NL and Danube floodplain reconnect RO, it has been vital to highlight the connections of the work to the wider EU policy landscape. In this wider context, the Green Deal goals are used as a justification for the large scope of diverse measures and actions. To evaluate whether the Green Deal goals are measurable, MERLIN has developed a monitoring manual and tested its applicability in all its case studies (Carvalho et al. 2022).

Lesson 8. RSPs bring together different actors. Paying attention to opposing opinions and conflict resolution and to include less powerful voices is important.

All cases have shown a great engagement with a large variety of stakeholders. The development of the RSPs has been a joint undertaking in all of them, although the amount of stakeholder groups and sectors involved and the level of involvement differed depending on the local situation. At the same time the need to create an RSP stimulated a wider dialogue with a larger group of stakeholders than what would have been the ‘standard’ approach for most cases.

The stakeholder engagement was examined through participating actors and level of engagement. Empowerment was not addressed, as RSPs are still a process in the making. However, questions about stakeholder control and decision-making power are crucial when pursuing transformative change. RSPs bring together a diverse group of stakeholders, allowing different voices and interests to be heard. In many RSPs, less powerful voices, such as local communities, are included in the form of community groups and associations.

However, this diversity also poses the challenge of whose voices and priorities are included in the final decisions (“just transformation”). Tensions and conflicts typically relate to economic and environmental goals. For example, the RSP Sorraia river restoration PT notes that agricultural producers are incentivized to “produce more, and in the larger areas possible”, while the agricultural and water regulators’ priorities are environmental conservation. In the Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI, tension arises between using land for restoration (ecological benefits) and using land for renewable energy (solar and wind farms). Win-win scenarios between environment and economy are being sought through collaborative planning, education and awareness raising as well as conflict resolution. Providing better and tailored information is important so that actors, such as farmers, understand the benefits of ecosystem services and Nature-based Solutions.

Lesson 9. Attracting private funding is a challenge as benefits of ecosystem and Nature-based Solutions remain inadequately accounted and acknowledged. Development of viable business models based on Nature-based Solutions is necessary for future work.

EU currently spends, on average, 2% of GDP in environmental protection expenditure (EEA 2023). Public funding both from EU, national and local levels is the main source of funding for restoration⁵. Currently, the availability of public funds for ecosystem restoration is highly diverse. Peatlands are a good example where there are national funds (e.g., Denmark, Finland and Scotland) to help facilitate the process of ecosystem restoration to support specific policy goals (e.g., carbon sequestration). For example, in Denmark, a budget of 535 million has been reserved to rewet 100,000 hectares of carbon-rich soil. In other countries, such national plans with financial support are not available, making freshwater ecosystem restoration much more difficult. In such cases where strong national policies and financial schemes are absent, we see resourcefulness in obtaining funds, especially EU funding such as LIFE projects, as a way of making progress, despite the uncertainty of the next

⁵ The term “restoration” of freshwater ecosystems may lead people astray in light of changing climate and land use and the time horizon of the RSP. Improving freshwater ecosystems must take these changing conditions into account to define realistic goals for both biodiversity and provision of ecosystem services. Restoration is often interpreted as returning to previous, less degraded conditions. Instead, improving freshwater ecosystems must take irreversible changes into account and anticipate impacts predicted in future scenarios. The Society for Ecological Restoration (SER) addresses these changing conditions in its mission and vision.

project proposal will come through (e.g., Lima floodplain forest restoration PT, which was recently successful). In these cases, the dedication of the project proposers to keep going is essential, yet a fragile point in the chain of progress.

RSPs acknowledge their dependence and need for public money also in the future and identify private funding as a potential source but not something that can replace public ones. Many RSPs recognize the crucial importance of private funding, but typically do not outline concrete strategies or business opportunities for private sector involvement in the future. There are a few notable exceptions. First, government strategies could support private sector participation. The Blue Belt DE RSP suggests that financial incentives and tax benefits to landowners could help to address land shortage. Upper Scheldt restoration BE suggests subsidies to convince farmers to implement grass-flower strips. In terms of business opportunities and also promoting a circular economy, using harvested biomass for biogas is identified as a business opportunity in the RSPs of Kvorning wetland rewetted DK, Emscher basin restoration DE and Upper Scheldt Restoration BE. There is a further need for the development of business models that result in viable funding and financing models for Nature-based Solutions. This enables them to gain traction with potential business partners and to attract investments from lenders. Development of business models could be supported by the government, as in the case of the Forth basin restoration UK RSP where the “Scottish Facility for Investment Ready Nature (FIRNS)”.

Development of viable income streams is vital to mainstream Nature-based Solutions because competing land uses (e.g., land is not restored, but a solar panel field is built) can offer landowners financially more attractive deals (e.g., yearly rent). Alternatively, income streams may be provided by government funds, such as agri-environmental schemes (e.g., Forth basin restoration UK). Overall, this points out that the financial benefits of restoration are not sufficiently clear certainly in monetary terms, while non-monetary may not be sufficiently convincing to attract private investors. A clear exception in this regard is the UK Peatland code (Forth basin restoration UK), a voluntary certification standard for UK peatland projects wishing to market the climate benefits of restoration. There is a similar need for developing biodiversity credits, although admittedly, the development of biodiversity credits is still in its infancy due to the challenges related to standardized measurements.

A common theme in the RSPs is the role of ecotourism as a potential business avenue, with activities like hiking, fishing, and hunting frequently mentioned. Overall, the identified business opportunities in this regard remain largely vague and broadly described, making it difficult for most of them to gain traction with potential business partners or attract significant investment from lenders.

Lesson 10. Thanks to holistic goals, the RSPs come with clear policy linkages.

The EU legislation has a profound policy-setting impact within EU countries. The Green Deal in particular has proven to be a powerful agenda-setter. The Green Deal is being implemented through, e.g., the European Climate Law and the new Nature Restoration Law, which will directly affect policymaking in the member states in years to come. For the MERLIN case studies located outside the EU (i.e. Bosnia-Herzegovina, Israel, UK), the need to address climate and biodiversity crisis should call for national and local policy initiatives. Furthermore, as part of the EU accession process, Bosnia Herzegovina is encouraged to align its environmental policies and standards with those of the EU, including the Nature Restoration Law.

Many RSPs underlined how the plans support existing policy targets set by major environmental EU regulations, e.g. Nature Restoration Law, Water Framework Directive (including the River Basin Management plans) and Habitats Directive. In addition to meeting existing policy goals, it was also important to know how freshwater restoration is included in/can contribute to other strategies and policies, such as climate adaptation, flood risk management and regional planning master plans. In few cases, the need for legislative reforms were highlighted, particularly in terms of changing the incentive systems of the agricultural production and CAP-subsidies to more sustainable forms such as the environmental schemes therein (e.g. Kampinos wetland rewetted PL, Tisza floodplain rewetted HU).

Furthermore, the RSP documents emphasized that the documents provide holistic approaches, roadmaps and working frameworks related to freshwater restoration (e.g. Danube floodplain restoration AT, Deba barrier removal ES, Lima floodplain forest restoration PT, Tisza floodplain rewetted HU) for policy-makers and societies. The approach emphasizes the role of government actors and policies for ensuring freshwater restoration. However, while the state and the government actors certainly have a major role to play in mainstreaming restoration and Nature-based Solutions into society, the participation of non-governmental actors is crucial to advance restoration in the pace and scale needed to meet the diverse water quality and restoration goals (e.g. Restoration Law goal of restoring at least 20% of the EU's land and sea areas by 2030).

There are many unanswered questions related to how to get the private sector (including landowners) to join restoration efforts. In other words, the question is about what kind of policies and policy-mixes are effective, and what role should information, regulation and economic instruments play in advancing freshwater restoration. Information provisioning and the need to regulate is highlighted in RSPs, but economic incentives are not widely discussed. There are a few exceptions, such as mentions of tax benefits (suggested in Blue Belt DE RSP) and subsidies (suggested in Upper Scheldt restoration BE and already a funding form in Forth basin restoration UK). As **lesson 9** highlights, the financial benefits of ecosystem services remain inadequately accounted and acknowledged, and thus, income streams from restoration remain smaller compared to other land uses. This emphasizes the urgent need to better understand the economics and finances around restoration and Nature-based Solutions and make them financially attractive, for example, through agri-environmental schemes.

It is also noteworthy that when large-scale initiatives such as Blue Belt DE are established and running, these can facilitate more policy changes. In this German case, the presence of Blue Belt supported legal changes and made restoration a feasible option for the shipping administration, which was not legally possible before.

Lesson 11. Monitoring is crucial to understand the effectiveness of measures and to foster policymaker and public support.

Long-term and reliable monitoring is needed to identify effective restoration measures and provide basic information that enables implementation of these measures elsewhere. Some RSPs explicitly mention the need for monitoring of Key Performance Indicators, such as the Beaver river engineering SE, Room for the Rhine NL, and the Forth basin restoration UK. However, this type of comprehensive monitoring data on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, biodiversity, and water quality but also social-economic impacts is crucial yet costly. For example, in the case of Blue Belt Germany, approximately 15% of implementation expenditure was allocated to monitoring (not including socio-economic monitoring). Furthermore, given the complexity of both natural and social systems, understanding outcomes and impacts of measures taken may take several years or even decades. At the same time, however, the resistance to nature restoration in the EU has grown, fuelled by the fears related to the perceived restoration costs and land use restrictions. The insufficiencies related to monitoring data should not stop expanding restoration actions, rather, it calls for the inclusion of monitoring schemes in all restoration projects and doing them in a smart, cost-effective way. Importantly, the monitoring results should be better communicated to policymakers and public at large. As highlighted by some RSPs (e.g., Emscher river restoration DE), citizens can also engage in monitoring themselves through citizen science, helping them to build a relationship with nature and understand occurring changes.

To ensure that the larger public supports restoration (i.e. views restoration policies as legitimate), there is a great need to expand the scope of socio-economic research and monitoring. The RSPs underline that restoration has important, positive linkages to health and wellbeing, as the restoration sites offer both nature experiences and encourage physical exercise. Data related to this and other socio-economic components of ecosystem restoration is essential to show the benefits of these measures in a multi-faceted manner.

Lesson 12. RSPs should be explicit about (the known) uncertainties and boundary conditions to be able to adapt and change plans as needed.

RSPs also identify uncertainties related to the biophysical, technical, policy, financial and social-ecological domains. These uncertainties are important to consider and show how both expected and unexpected changes in time may influence the final outcome in the long term. In the technical/biophysical domain, uncertainties surround measures that may not play out as expected or where species response is much slower than expected. Additionally, the role of invasive exotic species has often been mentioned as a problem of concern with limited tools to counterbalance these (cases 2, 5, 9, 10, 12, 13, 15, 17 – see Annex 7.1 for names). At a very practical level, there was also uncertainty regarding the availability of machines and workers for restoration, particularly in cases where expensive machinery with skilled labor was required.

In the policy and financial domain, there are worries related to the short lifespan of some running policy tools or financing tools (such as the national/regional schemes in Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI, the Kvorning rewetting scheme DK, and the Tzipori basin restoration IL) which also affected the time horizon of their RSPs (see chapter 3.4). Uncertainty in policymaking may hamper progress, e.g., in the Forth basin restoration UK, stakeholders were postponing restoration decisions, anticipating a possible change in funding for carbon sequestration credits, making restoration more profitable under a new – but still uncertain – funding scheme.

The uncertainties in the socio-ecological domain are especially related to changing opinions within the stakeholder groups, not only of individuals but also of the general group and in relation to changing political

settings after elections. Also, the lack of basic/specific knowledge with stakeholders and professionals working on water management may be hampering the progress and it seems that this aspect of awareness raising should be included in the RSPs as an important action point for success.

Lesson 13. Visualization is key for delivering the message of RSPs- but not yet sufficient.

Making good plans calls for easy access and readability of text, together with good visualization of concepts, visions and ideas is important to create successful and acceptable RSPs. Some of the RSPs have been able to already create clear figures and infographics that help communication of the RSPs and related plans to the wider group of stakeholders, e.g., Forth basin restoration UK, Tzipori basin restoration IL and the Tisza floodplain rewetting HU. Visualizations help stakeholders grasp concepts and visions for the longer future, facilitating further dialogue on them.

5.3 Summing up

The creation of the RSPs in MERLIN has proven an inspiring journey where people shared ideas and points of view in a structured manner and where the provided formats challenged them to think wider and broader than might have been the case under 'standard practises' and to do so together with a wider group of stakeholders. This did create sometimes challenging situations where people were to discuss topics outside their comfort zone or with groups that were previously not involved. Yet, the final result in many of these RSPs is that the overarching story and view of the future is much more holistic and rounded than at the start of the process. The sharing of experiences during the creation of the RSPs between the various case studies in MERLIN cluster meetings also provided additional support to take the extra leap into sometimes unknown new processes and topics.

All the individual regional scalability plans are available through the case study portal at the MERLIN website: [Case study portal - MERLIN project \(project-merlin.eu\)](https://project-merlin.eu)

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7 Annexes

7.1 Case study name, country, number, cluster and authors of the RSP

Number	Case Study	Country	Cluster	Authors of the RSP
CS01	Kvorning wetland rewetted DK	Denmark	Peatland & Wetlands	written by Naturstyrelsen with input from Annette Baattrup Pedersen, Aarhus University and support from Headquarter.
CS02	Deba barrier removal ES	Spain	Small streams and basins	Miriam Colls (University of Basque Country), Arturo Elosegui (University of Basque Country) and Iñaki Bañares (Gipuzkoa Provincial Council)
CS03	Beaver river engineering SE	Sweden	Peatland & Wetlands	Frauke Ecke (Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences), Karin Eklöf (Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences and Daniel Thorell (Swedish Forest Agency).
CS04	Room for the Rhine NL	Netherlands	Large transboundary rivers	Marieke de Lange (Rijkswaterstaat), Joost Backx (Rijkswaterstaat) and Gertjan Geerling (Deltares)
CS05	Kampinos wetland rewetted PL	Poland	Peatland & Wetlands	Małgorzata Siuta (Kampinos National Park), Karolina Lubowiecka (Kampinos National Park), Anna Andrzejewska (Kampinos National Park), Anna Wilińska (Kampinos National Park) and Julian Rudziński (Kampinos national park)
CS06	Hutovo Blato peatland rewetted BiH	Bosnia-Herzegovina	Peatland & Wetlands	Not received before the deadline
CS07a	Danube floodplain restoration AT	Austria	Large transboundary rivers	Silke-Silvia Drexler (BOKU), Iris Kempfer (viadonau), Alice Kaufmann (viadonau), Robert Tögel (viadonau), Andrea Funk (BOKU), Martin Tschikof (BOKU) and Thomas Hein (BOKU) BOKU=University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna
CS07b	Danube sidearm reconnect HU	Hungary	Large transboundary rivers	Tamás Gruber (WWF Hungary), Andrea Samu (WWF Hungary) and Tibor Erős (Balaton Limnological Research Institute)
CS08	Danube floodplain reconnect RO	Romania	Large transboundary rivers	Camelia Ionescu (WWF Romania), Iulia Puiu (WWF Romania), Mara Nilca (WWF), Albert Scriciu (GeoEcoMar)
CS09	Tisza floodplain rewetted HU	Hungary	Large transboundary rivers	Péter Kajner (WWF Hungary), Tamás Gruber (WWF Hungary) and Tamás Cselószki (WWF Hungary)
CS10	Blue Belt Germany DE	Germany	Large transboundary rivers	Michael Gerisch (Federal Institute of Hydrology), Isabell Lenz (Federal Institute of Hydrology), Elmar Fuchs (Federal Institute of Hydrology) and Sebastian Birk (University of Duisburg-Essen)
CS11	Emscher basin restoration DE	Germany	Small streams and basins	Nadine Gerner (EGLV), Svenja Karnatz (EGLV), Daniel Hering (University of Duisburg-Essen)

Number	Case Study	Country	Cluster	Authors of the RSP
CS12	Lima floodplain forest restoration PT	Portugal	Peatland & Wetlands	Francisco Lourenço Cerqueira Correia (Ponte de Lima municipality), Irene Trigueiro Lourenço (Ponte de Lima municipality), Vera Lúcia dos Santos Henriques (Ponte de Lima municipality), Estêvão Portela-Pereira (University of Lisbon) and Patricia María Rodríguez-González (University of Lisbon)
CS13	Sorraia river restoration PT	Portugal	Small streams and basins	Teresa Ferreira (ISA-ULisboa), Gonçalo Duarte (ISA-ULisboa), Leonor Santos (ISA-ULisboa) and José Maria Santos (ISA-ULisboa) All authors from School of Agronomy, University of Lisbon (ISA-ULisboa):
CS14	Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI	Finland	Peatland & Wetlands	Maria Ojanen (Finnish Environment Institute), Katri Rankinen (Finnish Environment Institute), Anna-Kaisa Ronkanen (Finnish Environment Institute), Tiina Ronkainen (Tapio), Kristian Meissner (Finnish Environment Institute) and Mirkka Visuri (Finnish Environment Institute)
CS15	Tzipori basin restoration IL	Israel	Small streams and basins	Tal Marciano Ratner (Kishon Drainage and River Authority - KRDA), Yaron Hershkovitz (Tel Aviv University), Avital Katz (Tel Aviv University), Revital Riklin (Center for Watershed, Runoff, and River Management -Aigma), Michal Grosman (DHVMED) and Lihi Luzon-Beranan (DHVMED).
CS16	Upper Scheldt restoration BE	Belgium	Small streams and basins	Pieter Boets (Province of East Flanders) and Marie Anne Eurie Forio (University of Ghent)
CS17	Forth basin restoration UK	United Kingdom	Peatland & Wetlands Small streams and basins	Charlotte Neary (Forth Rivers Trust), Niall Provan (Forth Rivers Trust), Ewan Lawrie (Nature Scot), Iain Sime (Nature Scot), Keith Mathews (James Hutton Institute) and Amy Pickard (UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology)

7.2 Timetable (Sept 2023 – Sept 2024) to prepare the final RSPs

When	What	Who
Sep 23	Presenting ROADMAP and interact with CS during APM	Deltares & SYKE
Oct 23	Review interim RSPs and feedback to CS Involve WP3, WP4 leads	SYKE & Deltares
Nov 23	Cluster meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CS to read D2.2 Summary of feedback CS to prepare draft programme for live stakeholder event Presenting template	SYKE & Deltares (CS get homework)
Dec 23	Template for FINAL RSP, RSP self-assessment	SYKE
Nov 23 – Jan 24	1st Stakeholder event	Each CS
Dec 23 – Feb 24	Prepare draft RSP, RSP self-assessment	Each CS
Jan 24	Q & A meetings (2)	SYKE, Deltares
Jan 24	Brainstorm on visualisation	UDE, BOKU, SYKE, Deltares, JHI, WWF
Feb 24	APM Vienna: Status update on RSP and stakeholder events, start with visualisations	SYKE, Deltares and all CS
Mar – Apr 24	Reviewing draft version of the final RSP and organizing feedback	Mar – Apr 24
Apr - May 24	2nd Stakeholder event	Each CS
May - Jun 24	Final RSP revision	Each CS
Jun - Jul 24	Preparing draft D2.4	SYKE & Deltares
Jul - Aug 24	Review	UDE, WP3F and WP4 leads
Sep 24	Finalise D2.4 and each individual RSP (national language, EN)	SYKE & Deltares

7.3 Annex 1 case study feedback form

Case study:

Reviewed by:

Date of review:

General comments	Feedback
Is the plan of use after the MERLIN project has finished?	
Can the plan be shared externally with the wider society?	
Readability of the plan	
Is it ambitious?	
Is it inspiring and inviting?	
Is it specific and concrete?	
Is it pleasant to read?	

Chapter	Title	Feedback
1	For the reader	
2	Focus of the RSP	
2.1	Regional characteristics	
2.2	Justification for the region	
2.3	Linkages and synergies with other initiatives	
	Relevant materials	Provided YES / NO
3	Stakeholders of the RSP (who)	
3.1	Describe the main stakeholders in this template.	
3.2	Update the stakeholder mapping template.	
4	Green Deal goals	
4.1	SMART Green Deals relevant for the region: primary goals	
4.2	SMART Green Deals relevant for the region: secondary goals	
	Relevant materials	Provided YES / NO
5	From general goals to actions	
5.1	Climate Goal	
5.2	Biodiversity Goal	
5.3	Inclusivity goal	
5.4	Other primary/secondary goal	
5.5	Other primary/secondary goal	
5.6	Identify the responsible stakeholders and their roles	
	Relevant materials	Provided YES / NO
	Add graphics as a summary	
6	Timeline	
7	Budget	
8	Uncertainties and assumptions/ boundary conditions	

Additional general comments:

Detailed comments are given as track changes in the document.